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Review

Effect of prenatal phthalate exposure on fetal development and maternal/neonatal health consequences: A systematic review

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Exposure to phthalates adversely affects maternal, fetal, and infant health.
- Phthalates are considered to be endocrine disruptors.
- Exposure to phthalates during pregnancy is associated with pregnancy complications.
- Prenatal exposure to phthalates is linked to neurodevelopmental disorders.
- The results of this review provide evidence for reducing exposure to phthalates.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The ubiquitous presence of phthalate compounds in cosmetics, personal care products and plastics commonly used in toys, food packaging or household products, results in human exposure with adverse effects on reproductive health and fetal development. Following the PRISMA methodology, this systematic review analyzes the effect of prenatal phthalate exposure on major pregnancy complications, such as gestational diabetes, pregnancy-induced hypertension, fetal growth restriction and preterm birth, and its role in fetal neurodevelopment. This review includes >100 articles published in the last 10 years, showing an association between maternal exposure

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Fetal growth restriction
Preterm birth
Infant neurodevelopment

to phthalates and the risk of developing pregnancy complications. Phthalates are negatively associated with motor skills and memory, and also increase the risk of delayed language acquisition, autism spectrum disorder traits, and behavioral deficits, such as attention deficit hyperactivity disorder in children prenatally exposed to phthalates. Di (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate and its metabolites (mono(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, mono(3-carboxypropyl) phthalate, mono(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate, mono(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate) are the main compounds associated with the above-mentioned pregnancy complications and fetal neurodevelopmental disorders. In addition, this review discusses the molecular mechanisms responsible for various pregnancy complications and neurodevelopmental disorders, and the critical window of exposure, in order to clarify these aspects. Globally, the most common molecular mechanisms involved in the effects of phthalates are endocrine disruption, oxidative stress induction, intrauterine inflammation, and DNA methylation disorders. In general, the critical window of exposure varies depending on the pathophysiology of the complication being studied, although the first trimester is considered an important period because some of the most vulnerable processes (embryogenesis and placentation) begin early in pregnancy. Future research should aim to understand the specific mechanism of the disruptive effect of each component and to establish the toxic dose of phthalates, as well as to elucidate the most critical period of pregnancy for exposure and the long-term consequences for human health.

1. Introduction

Phthalates constitute a group of chemicals employed in the plastics industry to help dissolve other materials and act as plasticizers, which are incorporated into plastic goods products during the manufacturing process to enhance their flexibility and durability (FDA, n.d.). These compounds are classified as esters of phthalic acid and can be categorized into two groups based on the number of carbon atoms in their backbone (Kumar et al., 2015): low molecular weight phthalates (LMWP), which are commonly used in cosmetics and personal care items; and high molecular weight phthalates (HMWP), commonly employed as plasticizers in toys, food packaging, household products and medical devices (Mesquita et al., 2021). The main paternal phthalates and their metabolites that will appear throughout this review are summarized in Fig. 1.

The extensive production and utilization of phthalates has resulted in their widespread distribution in the environment, contaminating water, soil, and air, thereby resulting in human exposure with detrimental health consequences (Mondal et al., 2022). These compounds enter the human body primarily through the skin, respiratory and digestive systems. Upon exposure, phthalates are quickly metabolized to monoesters by esterase and lipase in the gut and other tissues. They are then enzymatically catalyzed by UDP-glucuronosyl-transferase to form hydrophilic glucuronide conjugates, which are readily excreted in the urine (Y.J. Zhang et al., 2021). Due to their short half-life of hours to days, phthalates are rapidly eliminated from the body. The most usual method to assess human exposure to phthalates is the analysis of phthalate metabolites in urine samples (Meeker et al., 2009). However, other biological matrices such as umbilical cord blood or breast milk are also employed in human exposure studies to quantify phthalate metabolites (Meeker et al., 2009).

A growing evidence from animal, human and in vitro models has revealed the deleterious effects of phthalates on reproductive health and fetal development (Meeker et al., 2009). The various metabolites of phthalates alter normal hormonal homeostasis and act as endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) (Mesquita et al., 2021) through the different hormonal axes, including the hypothalamic-pituitary, thyroid, adrenal, testicular or ovarian axis (Ullah et al., 2023). Phthalates exert their effects through different molecular mechanisms, such as oxidative stress, cytotoxicity, immunotoxicity (Ullah et al., 2023), changes in DNA methylation (Zhao et al., 2015), disruption of miRNA expression and modulation of transcription of genes involved in different molecular pathways (Martínez-Ibarra et al., 2019), or the activation of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPARs) related to glucose homeostasis (Benjamin et al., 2017; Martin et al., 2022). The pathophysiological mechanisms induced by phthalate exposure have consequences in pregnant women, a population of special concern due to the heightened vulnerability of the developing fetus (Lyche et al., 2009).

In light of recent data on the harmful effects of phthalates in animal models regarding their endocrine disruption effects, and potential damage to human health, regulatory agencies such as the US Food and Drug Administration and the European Medicines Agency have established maximum daily exposure limits for LMWPs. These include a tolerable daily exposure of 4.0 mg/kg body weight/day for diethyl phthalate (DEP) and 0.01 mg/kg body weight/day for dibutyl phthalate (DBP) (Broe et al., 2017). In addition, the low observed adverse effect level (LOAEL) was set to be at 1016–1375 mg/kg body weight/day for DEP and ≥ 2 mg/kg body weight/day for DBP in experimental studies (European Medicines Agency, n.d.).

Recent evidence suggests that phthalates may have an impact on pregnancy complications and consequences on the growing fetus. The purpose of this systematic review is to evaluate the association between prenatal phthalate exposure and major pregnancy complications, specifically gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), pregnancy-induced hypertension (PIH), fetal growth restriction (FGR) and preterm birth (PTB). Additionally, this review aims to provide an overview of phthalates role in the neurodevelopment of infants prenatally exposed to these compounds. Concretely, this article reviews human studies published within the last 10 years, focusing on different aspects, such as perinatal outcomes and pathophysiological mechanisms depending on the time of exposure.

2. Materials and methods

The present systematic review was conducted according to the PRISMA (Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analysis) statement (Shamseer et al., 2015; Liberati et al., 2009), according to the 2009 guidelines and the updated 2020 PRISMA methodology (Page et al., 2021). The research team defined and evaluated the following items: definition of the research question, hypothesis and objectives; bibliographic search; data collection, appraisal, synthesis and comparison; critical appraisal of the selected scientific papers; and finally, analysis of the main findings and conclusions including the strengths and weaknesses of these studies. This review focuses on the harmful effects of phthalate exposure during pregnancy on fetal development and maternal or neonatal health, resulting in gestational diabetes or weight gain, pregnancy-induced hypertension, fetal growth restriction, preterm birth, and infant neurodevelopment. The differences in the populations studied, the variables assessed, the phthalates analyzed, and the different times of sample collection led us to decide not to perform a meta-analysis. PubMed (MeSH), Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials and Embase, were the electronic databases consulted to collect the data. We performed an initial search using descriptors (as MeSH terms or not) and similar terms with the Boolean operators (AND/OR) in multiple combinations (see Supplemental 1. Methodology). All terms were adapted for the databases consulted for

Fig. 1. Main parent phthalates and their metabolites mentioned in this review.

Abbreviations. DOP: di-n-octylphthalate; DEHP: di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate; DMP: dimethyl phthalate; DBP: dibutyl phthalate; BBzP: benzyl butyl phthalate; DPP: dipentyl phthalate; DEP: diethyl phthalate; DIBP: diisobutyl phthalate; DIDP: diisodecyl phthalate; DnOP: di-n-octylphthalate; DINP: diisononyl phthalate; MCPP: mono-(3-carboxypropyl) phthalate; MEHP: mono(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate; MMP: mono-methyl phthalate; MBP: monobutyl phthalate; MBzP: monobenzyl phthalate; MPP: monopentyl phthalate; MEP: monoethyl phthalate; MiBP: monoisobutyl phthalate; MHiBP: mono-hydroxy-isobutyl phthalate; MCNP: monocarboxy-isononyl phthalate; MOCP: mono-carboxy-isoocetyl phthalate; MiNP: mono-isononyl phthalate; MCOP: monocarboxyoctyl phthalate; MONP: mono oxononyl phthalate; MEHHP: mono(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate; MEOHP: mono-(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate; MECPP: mono(2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) phthalate; MCPP: mono-(3-carboxypropyl) phthalate; MHBP: mono-3-hydroxybutyl phthalate; MOBP: mono-3-oxo-n-butyl phthalate; MHPP: mono(4-hydroxypentyl) phthalate; MOPP: mono (4-oxopentyl) phthalate; MCEP: mono(2-carboxyethyl) phthalate; MCBP: mono(4-carboxybutyl) phthalate.

this review.

Inclusion criteria were papers written in English (with no geographical restrictions) published between June 26, 2013 and June 26, 2023, with evidence of phthalate exposure and health outcomes during the perinatal period; the presence of the selected terms in the title/abstract or in all fields; original research conducted in humans; original manuscripts or meta-analysis with JCR impact factor. The type of manuscripts selected were classical article, clinical study, clinical trials, comparative study, case-control and longitudinal cohort. Pre-clinical studies, case report studies, individuals with genetic alterations and studies reporting variables unrelated to the effects of phthalate exposure were excluded. Selected outcomes were evidence of maternal gestational diabetes, obesity, pregnancy-induced hypertension, fetal growth restriction, preterm birth, and infant neurodevelopmental outcomes following phthalate exposure during pregnancy. All citations were collected and imported into Mendeley Citation Manager.

Researchers E.N.T., G.S., S.F.M. and L.A.T. performed the initial selection of original manuscripts by screening titles and abstracts, creating a reference list of papers on the topics evaluated in this review using Rayyan software to perform systematic reviews (Ouzzani et al., 2016). Four investigators (E.N.T., G.S., S.F.M. and L.A.T.) performed each stage of study selection, deleted duplicate entries and reviewed studies as excluded or requiring further assessment. All data were extracted by two investigators (E.N.T., L.A.T.) and cross-checked by the other two investigators (S.F.M. and G.S.). In case of discrepancies in the selected studies, we opted for reconciliation by team discussion and decision of V.A.F. or O.G.A. The information evaluated from each study was: first author, year of publication, objective, study design and study population, measured variables, and description of the sample collected. The main results/findings, conclusions and strengths and limitations were also analyzed. The primary outcomes were the number of mothers diagnosed with gestational diabetes, weight gain, pregnancy-induced

Fig. 2. PRISMA flowchart for the selected studies.

hypertension, newborns with fetal growth restriction, number of preterm births, and neurodevelopmental changes measured by questionnaires. All authors critically appraised the studies selected according to the inclusion criteria, and analyzed the methodology and main results.

This systematic review protocol was registered in PROSPERO (International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews), on June 27, 2023 with the registration number CRD42023446058. Available from: https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospero/display_record.php?RecordID=446058.

The quality of evidence was assessed according to the GRADE (Grades of Recommendation, Assessment, Development and Evaluation) approach which describes four levels of quality: high, moderate, low, and very low (Guyatt et al., 2011). The quality of evidence was evaluated by all the authors (at least 2 authors independently for each section) (Supplemental Tables S1, S2, S3, S4 and S5), focusing on the study design, number of subjects, risk of bias, inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, and observed relative or absolute effects. Disagreements were resolved by consensus-based discussion.

3. Results

3.1. Characteristics of the included studies

After a bibliographic search of the databases, 447 published articles were identified and are listed in the Materials and Methods section. After removing duplicate articles (72), the abstract and title of the potentially relevant 375 articles were reviewed. After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 163 references were eliminated. The full text of the remaining 212 references was carefully analyzed and 100 articles were removed because they were not related to the topic of the study, the studies were preclinical, or tested compounds other than phthalates. Finally, 107 studies were eligible and included in this systematic review, as is shown in the flowchart in Fig. 2.

3.2. Phthalate exposure in pregnancy, gestational diabetes and gestational weight gain

The results of the reviewed studies showed that phthalate exposure may affect glucose metabolism by inhibiting insulin signaling, glucose uptake and oxidation, leading to insulin resistance status (Radke et al.,

Fig. 3. Pathophysiological mechanisms induced by prenatal exposure to phthalates in relation to major obstetric complications.

Abbreviations. COX-2: cyclooxygenase-2; CRH: corticotropin-releasing hormone; GLUT-2: glucose transporter-2; IL: interleukin; OHdG: 8-hydroxydeoxyguanosine; PIGF: placental growth factor; PPARs: peroxisome proliferator activated receptors; PR: progesterone receptors; RAAS: renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system; sFit-1: soluble fms-like tyrosine kinase-1.

2020). The main mechanism has been focused on the activation of PPARs, which are involved in adipogenesis and regulate lipid and glucose homeostasis, with consequent damage to pancreatic beta-cell growth (Benjamin et al., 2017). According to another recently described mechanism, DBP may affect insulin secretion by disrupting P13K expression and Akt phosphorylation, leading to a reduction in pancreatic GLUT-2 and a decrease in this insulin signaling pathway (Deng et al., 2018). In addition, phthalates alter steroid hormone metabolism and exhibit estrogenic activity leading to insulin resistance (Sathyanarayana et al., 2017). Moreover, recent studies describe phthalates as obesogenic, increasing the number and size of fat cells, altering the basic metabolic pathways and regulating hunger, satiety and food choice (Muscoigiuri et al., 2017). A summary of the main effects of phthalate exposure on the outcomes addressed in this review is shown in Fig. 3.

Epidemiologic studies evaluating the association between phthalate exposure and glucose levels during pregnancy have yielded inconsistent results (Table 1). Three recent studies conducted in China showed significant evidence that the presence of phthalates in serum or urine during early and late pregnancy increased the risk of GDM (Liang et al., 2022; W. Chen et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023).

Fisher et al. found an association between the presence of mono- (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (MEHP) and mono-carboxy-isooctyl phthalate (MCOP) in first trimester (T1) serum samples and 120-min plasma glucose in a cohort of 232 pregnant women (Fisher et al., 2018). In addition, a recent study conducted in Mexico found associations between urinary levels of some phthalates and miRNA expression levels associated with GDM. miRNAs play an important role in controlling metabolic processes by modulating the expression of genes that are involved in metabolic pathways (Martínez-Ibarra et al., 2019). Therefore, environmental exposure to phthalates may disrupt the expression of miRNAs associated with GDM.

A link between phthalate metabolites and glucose intolerance has also been described by Shaffer et al., who found an association between the median urinary levels of mono-ethyl phthalate (MEP) levels in T1, third trimester (T3) and GDM, with a possible correlation to racial groups (Shaffer et al., 2019). In the same line, Todd et al. found associations between T2 urinary MEP and mono-isobutyl phthalate (MiBP)

with an impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) and mono-3-hydroxybutyl phthalate (MHBP) with an increased in GDM (James-Todd et al., 2016; James-Todd et al., 2022). Conversely, they found an inverse association between higher concentrations of sum of di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate (ΣDEHP) in T2 and reduced odds of IGT (James-Todd et al., 2016). These differences described in the same study may be related to the different mechanisms of action of each metabolite on PPAR-associated pathways. However, the first trimester of pregnancy appears to be a critical period during which phthalate exposure increases the risk of altered metabolic outcomes (Gao et al., 2021).

The same authors also found a positive association between urinary MEP at T2 and IGT but an inverse association between MiBP and IGT in a population of pregnant women following infertility treatment, but such different results were found in a subfertile population with risk factors for glucose dysregulation. Moreover, elevated levels of MiBP, associated with fish consumption, suggest a healthier diet in these patients (James-Todd et al., 2018).

Conversely, Shapiro et al. (Shapiro et al., 2015) found no association between urinary phthalates and glucose tolerance diseases in pregnancy, and another study conducted by Robledo et al. (Robledo et al., 2015) found an inverse association between phthalate concentrations and glucose levels. However, these studies only measured phthalate exposure at one time point during pregnancy (T1) and did not take into account risk factors associated with GDM or elevated glucose levels in pregnancy.

Phthalate exposure has also been associated with increased gestational weight gain (GWG) and overweight during pregnancy (Bellavia et al., 2017; Valvi et al., 2015; Pacyga et al., 2023; Deierlein et al., 2022; Boyer et al., 2023), but not all studies were consistent with these findings (Philips et al., 2020) (Table 2).

This inconsistency of the reported results may be explained by the fact that each sample in the different studies was collected at a different time of gestation, so the window of exposure was variable, and the matrices used for analysis were different (serum or urine). The timing of exposure may also be important because insulin resistance and glucose intolerance increase as pregnancy progresses. In addition, it has been described that the short half-life of phthalate metabolites in urine is 24–48 h, so a single determination may not be sufficient to provide

Table 1
Clinical studies based on gestational diabetes after exposure to phthalates during pregnancy.

Author(s) (year)/country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
Robledo et al. (2015)/USA	To assess the association between phthalate metabolite concentration in urine and blood glucose levels during early pregnancy	Longitudinal case control	72 pregnant women with a mean gestational age of 12.8 weeks at enrolment GDM (n = 15) Controls (n = 57)	- Urinary phthalate metabolites concentrations - Blood glucose levels	Inversely association between highest urinary concentrations (3rd tertile) of MiBP (tertile: 15.3 µg/L, $\beta = -18.3$, 95 % CI: -35.4 , -1.2) and MBzP (tertile: 30.3 µg/L, $\beta = -17.3$, 95 % CI: -34.1 , -0.4) and blood glucose levels at the time of GDM screening.	No association between phthalate metabolites concentration in urine and blood glucose levels during early pregnancy	Very low +/++++
Shapiro et al. (2015)/Canada	To assess the associations between plasticizers and metals in early pregnancy with IGT and GDM in a Canadian pregnancy cohort.	Longitudinal case control	1247 Women of Maternal-Infant Research on Environmental Chemicals (MIREC) study, singleton delivery and no pre-existing diabetes GDM (n = 48) IGT (n = 59) controls (n = 160)	Urine sample (T1): - 11 phthalate metabolites - Total BPA - Four metals (lead, cadmium, mercury and arsenic) - IGT and GDM Chemical concentrations were grouped by quartiles → logistic regression	Arsenic exposure → elevated odds of GDM in the highest quartile (OR = 3.7, 95 % CI = 1.4–9.6) A significant dose–response between arsenic and odds of GDM No associations between phthalates or BPA or other metals with IGT or GDM	Maternal arsenic exposure is a risk factor for GDM No association between phthalates and glucose tolerance diseases in pregnancy	Very low +/++++
James-Tod et al. (2016)/USA	To evaluate the association between risk factors linked to GMD and urinary phthalate metabolites	Longitudinal case-control	350 women participating in Lifecodes pregnancy cohort delivered at term IGT (n = 47) Controls (n = 303)	Urine sample at 4 time points: 9.9/17.9/26.1/35.3 weeks gestation. Quartiles of phthalate metabolites and continuous T1 BMI and late T2 blood glucose and IGT Multivariable logistic regression for phthalate levels and GWG and IGT = glucose ≥ 140 mg/dL after 50-g glucose load test	No associations between phthalates at T1 and BMI Association between MEP concentrations across pregnancy and excessive GWG (95 % CI: 0.98, 4.79) Association between MEP at T2 and increased odds of IGT (OR: 7.18; 95 % CI: 1.97, 26.15) Inverse association between Σ DEHP and IGT (OR: 0.25; 95 % CI: 0.08, 0.85)	GWG and IGT were associated with higher exposure to MEP - Higher DEHP levels associated with reduced odds of IGT.	Low ++/++++
James-Todd et al. (2018)/USA	To evaluate the association between phthalate and pregnancy glucose levels in women attending assisted reproduction	Longitudinal case control	245 pregnant women: OGTT <140 mg/dL (n = 200) OGTT ≥ 140 mg/dL (n = 45)	Urinary phthalates from single spot urine samples collected in T1 and T2 50-g glucose challenge tests at 24–28 weeks gestation. Multivariable linear regression for associations between 7 phthalates in quartiles and mean glucose	18 % of women: glucose levels ≥ 140 mg/dL. Positive association between MEP at T2 and glucose levels. Inverse association between MiBP and glucose levels	Subfertile women showed a significant association between MEP and MiBP with higher glucose levels during pregnancy	Low ++/++++
Fisher et al. (2018)/UK	To assess the relationship between maternal serum levels of phthalate metabolites and phenols at 10–17 weeks of pregnancy and glucose metabolism at 28 weeks of gestation	Prospective observational study case control (Cambridge Baby Growth Study)	232 women: GDM (n = 47) Controls (n = 185)	Serum sample at T1 - 16 phthalate metabolites and 9 phenols (including BPA) with chromatography/tandem mass spectrometry. - OGTT at 28 weeks	Women without GDM → positive association between MEHP at T1 and MCiOP with 120-min plasma glucose ($\beta = 0.268$ and 0.183 ; $p = 0.0002$ and 0.010 , respectively) TCS at T1 was inversely associated with GDM (95 % confidence interval 0.34–0.86, $p = 0.010$)	Phthalates rise glycaemia during pregnancy	Low ++/++++
Martínez-Ibarra et al. (2019)/Mexico	To explore if BPA and phthalates exposure alters serum levels of miRNAs associated with GDM risk	Longitudinal case control	40 pregnant women at T2 GDM (n = 18) Controls (n = 22)	Serum levels of miRNAs associated with GDM (miR-9-5p, miR-16-5p, miR-29a-3p and miR-330-3p) and urinary levels of phthalate	Patients with GDM: higher levels of miR-9-5p, miR-29a-3p and miR-330-3p Phthalates in 97–100 % of urine samples	- Positive correlation between urinary phthalate levels and miRNAs expression levels associated with GDM	Low ++/++++

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Table 1 (continued)

Author(s) (year)/country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
				metabolites (MBP, MiBP, MBzP, MEHP) and BPA in both groups	MEHP and BPA: higher in non-diabetics than in GDM patients (p = 0.03, p = 0.02). Positive correlations: MBzP and miR-16-5p (p < 0.05), MEHP and miR-29a-3p (p < 0.05). Negative correlations: MBP and miR-29a-3p (p < 0.0001, p < 0.05), MiBP and miR-29a-3p (p < 0.01)	- Women with GDM displayed a significant up-regulation of miR-9-5p, miR-29a-3p y miR-330-3p	
Shaffer et al. (2019)/USA	To study the relationship between 11 urinary phthalate metabolites, GDM, IGT and continuous blood glucose concentration during pregnancy	Longitudinal case control	705 pregnant women: GDM (n = 60) IGT and an average GLT of 113.6 ± 27.7 mg/dL (n = 90)	- The odds of GDM and IGT in relation to IQR → logistic regression - Phthalate metabolites concentrations at T1 and T3 - Sensitivity analyses → interactions between exposure and race	Positive correlation between MEP and GDM: MEP: [OR: 1.61 (95 % CI: 1.10, 2.36)]. Race-specific associations in Asians	- Association between MEP and GDM. - A link between phthalate metabolites and glucose intolerance, with possible relation to racial groups	Low ++/++++
Gao et al. (2021)/China	To assess the association of gestational levels of phthalate with metabolic risk	Longitudinal case control	3273 women: HDOP (n = 194) GDM (n = 428)	3 urine and serum samples in each trimester for 7 phthalate metabolite measurements HI to assess the cumulative risk of multiple phthalate coexposures. Variables: HDOP, GDM, and GWG.	Phthalate at T1 → elevated blood pressure and FPG at T3 and GWG HI value at T1 → positive association with BP, FPG, and GWG. HI at T1 increased the risks of GDM (OR = 1.34, 95 % CIs = 1.02–1.75) and excessive GWG (OR = 1.76, 95 % CIs = 1.41–2.19)	Single and combined phthalates in early pregnancy raised blood glucose, pressure and GWG	Low ++/++++
Zukin et al. (2022)/USA	To evaluate the association of 11 prenatal urinary phthalate metabolites and GDM, IGT, continuous plasma glucose level, GWG	Longitudinal case control	415 pregnant Latina women enrolled in the Center for the Health Assessment of Mothers and Children of Salinas (CHAMACOS) cohort study. IGT (n = 49) GDM (n = 31) Excess GWG (n = 223)	Phthalate metabolite levels measured via mass spectrometry from two urine samples in the end of the first and second trimester. Multiple regression	Association between MEP concentrations and an increased odds of excessive GWG (OR: 1.1, 95 % CI: 1.0 to 1.3). No association between phthalate metabolite and maternal glucose metabolism	Increased urinary concentrations of MEP were linked to excessive GWG. No association between prenatal phthalate levels and increased odds for hyperglycemia, IGT, or GDM.	Low ++/++++
Liang et al. (2022)/China	To examine the association between phthalate exposure and the risk of GDM	Longitudinal case control	200 pregnant women at 24–28 weeks' gestation: GDM (n = 100) Controls (n = 100)	- 11 plasticizer metabolites in urine sample in each trimester - Fasting blood glucose and fasting insulin in blood at T1	GDM group → significant higher MEHP and methylerythritol cyclophosphate concentrations Significant MEHP–GDM associations The GDM and MEHP dose–response relationships diverged significantly in <35 years' women and those >35 years	Phthalate exposure increases the risk of GDM	Low ++/++++
James-Todd et al. (2022)/USA	To evaluate the association between phthalate biomarkers with degrees of maternal glucose intolerance	Longitudinal case control	606 women: Normoglycemia (n = 136) IGT (n = 296) GDM (n = 174)	19 metabolites of urinary phthalates at T1-T3. Multivariable logistic regression adjusting for potential confounders.	Associations: High MCP levels at T1 decreased odds of GDM (Q4 vs. Q1: 0.30; 95 % CI: 0.13, 0.67) and IGT (Q4 vs. Q1 OR: 0.37; 95 % CI: 0.17, 0.79) High MiBP at T2	Phthalate biomarkers showed trimester-specific associations with glycaemic outcomes	Low ++/++++

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Table 1 (continued)

Author(s) (year)/country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
W. Chen et al. (2022)/China	To evaluate the association between phthalate exposure during early pregnancy and GDM in rural pregnant women	Longitudinal case control	Controls (n = 338) GDM (n = 338)	Urine samples at T1 GDM diagnosis at 24–28 weeks of gestation.	increased IGT (Q4 vs. Q1 OR: 2.07; 95 % CI: 1.06, 4.07) Association between MHBP at T2 with increased GDM (Q2 v. Q1 OR: 3.21; 95 % CI: 1.54, 6.87) Significant association between urinary concentrations of MOP, MBzP, MEOHP, MECPP, and GDM Logistic regression: association between MEOHP in the urine and GDM (OR = 1.55; 95 % CI: 1.00–2.39). EOHP concentrations >15.6 µg/L positively associated with GDM	Urinary concentrations of MOP, MBzP, MEOHP, MECPP associated with GDM. MEOHP levels of 15,6 µg/L associated to GDM	Low ++/++++
Wang et al. (2023)/China	To assess the concentrations of seven phthalate metabolites in pregnant women and their association with the risk of GDM and blood glucose levels.	Longitudinal case control	Controls (n = 62) GDM (n = 139) with GDM	Serum phthalate metabolite concentrations at T2 and T3 and blood glucose	Concentrations: MBP: 4.08 ng/mL MEHP: 1.28 ng/mL MiBP: 1.20 ng/mL Significant associations between MBP ($\beta = 2.24$, 95 % CI: 1.02, 5.07) and MiBP ($\beta = 1.84$, 95 % CI: 1.03, 3.31) and the incidence of GDM. Serum MBP and MiBP levels positively associated with 2-h blood glucose levels.	Serum concentrations of MBP and MiBP in pregnant women significantly associated with the levels of 2-hour blood glucose	Low ++/++++

Abbreviations: BMI: body mass index; BPA: bisphenol A; DEHP: bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate; FPG: fasting plasma glucose; GDM: gestational diabetes mellitus; GLT: glucose loading test; GWG: gestational weight gain; HDOP: hypertensive disorders of pregnancy; HI: hazard index; IGT: impaired glucose tolerance; IQR: Interquartile range; MBP: monobutyl phthalate; MBzP: mono-benzyl phthalate; MCiOP: mono(carboxyisooctyl) phthalate; MCPP: mono-3-carboxypropyl phthalate; MECPP: mono(2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) phthalate; MEHP: mono(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate; MEOHP: mono(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate; MEP: mono-ethyl phthalate; MHBP: mono-3-hydroxybutyl phthalate; MiBP: mono-isobutyl phthalate; MOP: mono-octyl phthalate; OGTT: oral glucose tolerance test; T1: first trimester of pregnancy; T2: second trimester of pregnancy; T3: third trimester of pregnancy; TCS: triclosan.

Quality of evidence grades: high (++++), moderate (+++), low (++) , very low (+).

information about variations in phthalate metabolite levels throughout pregnancy due to their short half-life. Another explanation for the different results could be the characteristics and ethnicity of the populations, as the exposure to toxic levels was different if the study was conducted in industrialized areas or rural populations due to social and ethnic differences, and some studies included populations with a higher prevalence of overweight/obesity, which may develop GDM. High fat diet and low socioeconomic status were significant variables influencing the risk of developing GDM and overweight and were likely confounding factors within the studies. Other factors influencing phthalate concentrations were maternal age, education level, parity, passive smoking during pregnancy, sunscreen product use and season of urine collection. Moreover, some studies included small populations compared with other studies, making the results difficult to interpret and generalize (Robledo et al., 2015). Finally, different mechanisms of action of each phthalate metabolites on insulin resistance, such as PPAR-gamma pathways, may explain the genetic susceptibility to phthalate-mediated insulin resistance and the greater susceptibility of a specific population to the effects of toxic exposure.

Despite the controversial findings, there is growing concern that phthalate exposure alters glucose metabolism and increases GWG, leading to metabolic disease.

3.3. Phthalates and hypertensive disorders in pregnancy

In recent years there has been a growing interest in the role of phthalates in pregnancy-induced hypertension. Thirteen studies conducted in the last 10 years on PIH and changes in maternal blood pressure (BP) in relation to maternal exposure to phthalates were included in this review (see Table 3 for a summary of the main results).

Six observational studies evaluated the association between maternal phthalate exposure and PIH disorders. Five of them found a positive association between phthalate exposure and PIH (Soomro et al., 2021, 2023; Bedell et al., 2021; Cantonwine et al., 2016; Werner et al., 2015). Two of the studies were conducted by Soomro et al. and showed a positive association between PIH and prenatal exposure to monomethyl phthalate (MMP) (OR: 1.56; 95 % CI: 1.07–2.27, $p = 0.02$), MEP (OR: 1.47; 95 % CI: 1.01–2.14, $p = 0.04$), mono(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate (MEHHP) (OR: 1.45; 95 % CI: 1.04–2.02, $p = 0.02$), mono(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate (MEOHP) (OR: 1.48; 95 % CI: 1.05–2.09, $p = 0.02$), MEHP (OR: 1.29; 95 % CI: 0.99–1.68, $p = 0.05$) and monobutyl phthalate (MBP) (OR = 1.66; 95 % CI: 1.11–2.47, $p = 0.01$) (Soomro et al., 2021, 2023). Additionally, two other cohort studies also found a positive association between maternal exposure to MEP (OR 1.4; CI 1.09–1.79, $p = 0.01$), mono-3-carboxypropyl phthalate (MCPP) (OR 1.34; CI 1.09–1.79, $p = 0.01$), MiBP (OR 1.5; CI 1.01–2.22, $p = 0.04$), mono-benzyl phthalate (MBzP) (RR = 2.92; 95 % CI 1.15–7.41, $p = 0.01$) and PIH (Bedell et al., 2021; Werner et al., 2015). Cantonwine

Table 2
Clinical studies based on phthalates exposure and gestational weight gain in pregnancy.

Author(s)/ year (country)	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
Valvi et al. (2015)/ Spain	To evaluate the reproducibility of urinary phthalate metabolite concentrations and predictors of exposure in Spanish pregnant women	Longitudinal cohort	391 Pregnant women	14 phthalates metabolites in urine samples at T1 and T3. - Questionnaires on predictors and FFQ Linear mixed and regression models	The ICCs ranged from 0.24 to 0.07 and were higher for MBzP, MEP, MiBP, and lower for MEOHP and MEHHP. Association among overweight, lower education and social class, and less consumption of organic food with higher levels of some phthalate metabolites. The use of household cleaning products once per week during pregnancy was associated with 10–44 % higher urinary phthalate	Overweight, lower education and social class, less frequent consumption of organic food and household cleaning products are associated with higher levels of some phthalate metabolites.	Low ++/++++
Bellavia et al. (2017)/ USA	To assess the association between urinary phthalate metabolite concentrations and the distribution of BMI, and early GWG during early pregnancy	Longitudinal cohort	347 pregnant women at T1	- Urinary phthalate metabolites concentrations. Multivariable regression	Association between higher concentrations of MEP and a rightward shift of 2.8 kg/m ² at the 75th percentiles of BMI (lowest vs highest quartile, 95 % CI: 0.2–5.4) and 1.3 kg at the 75th percentiles of early GWG (lowest vs second quartiles, 95 % CI: 0.3–2.4). Significant right-shift in the upper tail of BMI and concentrations MBzP, MCP, and ΣDEHP.	MEP, MBzP, MCP, and ΣDEHP were cross-sectionally associated with 1st trimester BMI - MEP and ΣDEHP positively and inversely associated with early GWG, respectively.	Very low +/++++
Philips et al. (2020)/ USA	To assess the relationship between urinary concentrations of bisphenols and phthalates in early and mid-pregnancy and GWG.	Longitudinal cohort	1213 pregnant women	- Urinary concentrations of bisphenols and phthalates in early and mid-pregnancy - Maternal anthropometrics before and during pregnancy - Linear and logistic regressions	Association between higher levels of total maternal total bisphenols and bisphenol S and lower total gestational weight	Pregnancy exposure to bisphenols and phthalates was not associated with GWG	Low ++/++++
Deierlein et al. (2022)/ Mexico-USA	To study associations of prenatal phthalate exposure with maternal GWG and seven years post-delivery.	Longitudinal cohort	874 pregnant women enrolled in the Programming Research in Obesity, Growth Environment and Social Stress Study in Mexico City	15 urinary phthalate biomarkers at T2 and T3. GWG (T2 and T3), short-term weight (T3 and 1 year post-delivery), and long-term weight (1.5 years and 6–7 years post-delivery)	Association between: - lower GWG and urinary phthalates - prenatal urinary phthalates and maternal weight change at 12 months postpartum and from 18 months to 6–7 years follow-up	Prenatal exposure to phthalates was negatively associated with GWG and positively associated with long-term variation in maternal weight.	Low ++/++++
Pacyga et al. (2023)/ USA	To investigate associations of phthalate biomarkers with GWG.	Longitudinal cohort	299 pregnant women	19 phthalate/replacement metabolites in morning urine samples, collected monthly between 8 and 40 weeks gestation. Associations of ten biomarkers with GWG in all women and stratified by fetal sex.	Sums of metabolites of ΣDEHP, ΣDiNCH, and ΣDEHTP → inverse associations with GWG, some associations fetal sex-specific. ΣDEHP, ΣDEHTP, and MCP, along with sum of ΣDiNP and MBzP → association with lower and higher GWG, respectively.	Phthalates/ replacement biomarkers were associated with GWG in a fetal sex-specific manner.	Low ++/++++
Boyer et al.	To study the association between nine maternal	Longitudinal cohort	Case-control LIFECODES (n = 379), prospective	9 maternal phthalate metabolites in urine Total GWG	Concentrations of MCP and MBP → positive association	Positive association between phthalates and higher GWG,	Low ++/++++

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Author(s)/ year (country)	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
(2023)/ USA	phthalate metabolites and measures of GWG		birth cohort from Boston, Massachusetts (2006–2008).		with total GWG z-scores among women with obesity MBP showed potential non-linear relationship with GWG	especially among women with pre- pregnancy obesity	

Abbreviations. BMI: body mass index; DEHP: bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate; DEHTP: di(2-ethylhexyl) terephthalate; DiNCH: di(isononyl) cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate; DiNP: di(isononyl) phthalate metabolites; FFQ: food-frequency questionnaires; GWG: gestational weight gain; ICCs: intraclass correlation coefficients; MBP: mono-butyl phthalate; MBzP: mono-benzyl phthalate; MCPP: mono-3-carboxypropyl phthalate; MECPP: mono(2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) phthalate; MEHHP: mono-(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate; MEOHP: mono(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate; MEP: mono-ethyl phthalate; MiBP: mono-isobutyl phthalate; T1: first trimester of pregnancy; T2: second trimester of pregnancy; T3: third trimester of pregnancy.

Quality of evidence grades: high (++++), moderate (+++), low (++) , very low (+).

et al. found an association between maternal urinary MEP, Σ DEHP and the onset of preeclampsia (Cantonwine et al., 2016). However, the HOME study reported no relationship between maternal MCPP exposure and PIH (Vuong et al., 2021). In this case, it is important to note that PIH is estimated to affect 4 % to 8 % of pregnant women (Booker, 2020), so, the small sample size in this cohort study (Vuong et al., 2021), may be insufficient to find statistically significant results.

In addition, eight observational studies evaluated the association between maternal phthalate exposure and changes in BP during pregnancy. Three of them found an increase of diastolic BP (DBP) in those mothers with higher exposure to MBzP, MiBP and LMWP during pregnancy (Werner et al., 2015; Wu et al., 2021; Han et al., 2020). Nevertheless, two other studies found a negative association between maternal sum of DBP and di-n-octylphthalate (DNOP) urinary phthalates and dBP (Wu et al., 2021; Philips et al., 2019). In these studies, lack of data on preconception and first trimester blood pressure values (Wu et al., 2021), or possible misclassification of exposure (Philips et al., 2019) may be confounding factors. Regarding systolic BP (sBP), maternal Σ DEHP, MBP, MCPP, dimethyl phthalate (DMP), DEP, DBP and MEP were associated with high values of sBP (Gao et al., 2021; Bedell et al., 2021; Vuong et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2021). However, a cohort study of 152 pregnant women with simultaneous measurement of sBP and urinary phthalates found a negative association between maternal exposure to MEP, MiBP and sBP (Warembourg et al., 2019). Again, the limited sample size and the lack of a timeline for phthalate metabolite analysis and BP measurement may be confounding factors in this study.

With regard to phthalate exposure during the pregnancy, most studies evaluated exposure during the three trimesters of pregnancy (Gao et al., 2021; Han et al., 2020; Ferguson et al., 2015a) or at least during the first trimester (Bedell et al., 2021; Cantonwine et al., 2016; Philips et al., 2019; LaRocca et al., 2014). However, four of the reviewed studies evaluated phthalate exposure only from the second trimester (Soomro et al., 2021, 2023; Werner et al., 2015; Vuong et al., 2021; Warembourg et al., 2019). It is therefore of interest to examine phthalate concentrations of phthalates in all of the trimesters of pregnancy or, at least in the first trimester, as the first trimester represents a critical window of exposure for the induction of epigenetic changes (LaRocca et al., 2014) and placental damage (Ferguson et al., 2015a). In addition, single determinations give us poor information about the variability of phthalate metabolite concentrations throughout pregnancy due to their short half-life of approximately 24–28 h (Soomro et al., 2021; Bedell et al., 2021; Philips et al., 2019).

All the studies presented in this review evaluated a range of maternal phthalate metabolites in urine samples. As mentioned above, most of the studies analyzed phthalate concentrations at different time points during pregnancy to ensure a more realistic approximation due to the short half-life of phthalate metabolites in urine samples (Bedell et al., 2021; Philips et al., 2019). Nevertheless, the simultaneous evaluation of

multiple phthalate metabolites could lead to a co-exposure amplification bias (Wu et al., 2021). For these reasons, future studies should aim to analyze the concentration of the phthalate metabolites most associated with PIH in different biological matrices representing maternal phthalate exposure and take into account the pharmacokinetics of these metabolites.

Finally, several pathophysiological mechanisms have been described to explain the association between phthalate exposure and maternal hypertensive disorders (Fig. 3), mainly the endocrine disrupting effect through the rennin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, a major regulator of BP (Warembourg et al., 2019); the placental methylation disorders inducing aberrant genomic imprinting (Soomro et al., 2023; LaRocca et al., 2014), and the alteration of circulating placental angiogenic biomarkers (Ferguson et al., 2015a).

3.4. The role of phthalates in fetal growth restriction

Recent studies conducted in pregnant populations have investigated the risk of prenatal exposure to phthalates on fetal growth, reflecting increased attention to this area of research. Twenty-three studies on the association between prenatal exposure to phthalates and fetal growth conducted in the pregnant population in the last 10 years were included in this review. An overview of the main findings is presented in Table 4.

Seventeen studies found a negative association between maternal phthalate exposure and fetal growth, specifically for butyl-benzyl phthalate (BBzP) (Guo et al., 2022), DEHP (Guo et al., 2022; Santos et al., 2021; Miura et al., 2021; Ferguson et al., 2016), DMP (Guo et al., 2022), MiBP (Bloom et al., 2019), MEOHP (Ferguson et al., 2016; Bloom et al., 2019; Zhao et al., 2014, 2016), MEP (Bloom et al., 2019; Bommarito et al., 2021; Zang et al., 2023), mono-2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl phthalate (MECPP) (Ferguson et al., 2016), MEHHP (Zhao et al., 2015, 2014, 2016; Lenters et al., 2016), MCPP (Hu et al., 2021), Σ DEHP (Zhao et al., 2015, 2014; Hu et al., 2021), bis (2-ethoxyethyl) phthalate (DEEP) (Huang et al., 2014) and MBP (Zhao et al., 2014; Stevens et al., 2023a), the sum of di-n-butyl phthalate (Σ DBP) (Stevens et al., 2023a), mono-carboxy-isooctyl phthalate (MCOP) (Zang et al., 2023), and mono (2-carboxymethylhexyl) phthalate (MCMHP) (Zang et al., 2023). A case-control study conducted by Guo et al. showed a strong association between phthalate exposure and FGR, especially for DEHP (OR = 3.89; 95 % CI: 1.305–11.910, P = 0.015) (Guo et al., 2022). Furthermore, Bloom et al. found an association between prenatal exposure to MiBP (OR = 2.82; 95 % CI: 1.21–6.56), MEOHP (OR = 2.80; 95 % CI: 1.05–7.42) and an increased risk of small for gestational age (SGA) fetuses (Bloom et al., 2019). Similarly, Zang et al. found a positive association between MEP, MCOP, MCMHP and low birth weight (LBW) (Zang et al., 2023). Other groups found statistically significant reductions in estimated fetal weight (EFW) or birth weight in fetuses prenatally exposed to MBzP, MCPP, Σ DBP, Σ DEHP and MEHHP (Ferguson et al., 2016; Lenters et al., 2016; Hu et al., 2021; Stevens et al., 2023a). Nevertheless, three studies

Table 3

Summary of recent studies on the association between maternal exposure to phthalates and hypertensive disorders during pregnancy.

Author(s) (year)/ country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
Soomro et al. (2023)/ Canada	To study the association between PIH and prenatal phthalate exposure.	Cohort study	N = 420 pregnant women < 27 WG (Alberta Pregnancy Outcomes and Nutrition)	MMP, MEP, MBP, MiBP, MECPP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MEHP, MBzP, MCOP, MNP, MCNP and Σ DEHP phthalate determination in urine at T2 by HPLC-MS/MS. PIH diagnosis.	MMP (OR: 1.56, 95 % CI: 1.07–2.27, p = 0.02), MEP (OR: 1.34, 95 % CI: 1.08–1.68, p = 0.008), MEHHP (OR: 1.45, 95 % CI: 1.04–2.02, p = 0.02), MEOHP (OR: 1.48, 95 % CI: 1.05–2.09, p = 0.02) and MEHP (OR: 1.29, 95 % CI: 0.99–1.68, p = 0.05) were associated with PIH	Maternal exposure to phthalates at T2 was associated with PIH.	Low ++/++++
Soomro et al. (2021)/ France	To determine the association between PIH and phthalates exposure	Nested cross-sectional study (French EDEN mother-child cohort)	N = 604 pregnant women (23rd–28th WG of French EDEN mother-child cohort)	BP and 11 phthalate metabolites quantification in urine samples between the 23rd and 28th WG.	29 mothers (4.8 %) developed PIH. MEP and MBP were associated with PIH (OR = 1.47, 95 % CI: 1.01–2.14, p = 0.04 and OR = 1.66, 95 % CI: 1.11–2.47, p = 0.01; respectively). Increased concentrations of MBzP at T2 were associated with dBP (+0.5 mm Hg; 95 % CI: 0.1, 0.9). Increased Σ DEHP were associated with sBP (+0.7 mm Hg; 95 % CI: 0, 1.5) and Σ DBP were associated with dBP (–0.7 mm Hg; 95 % CI: –1.5, 0.0)	Prenatal exposure to some phthalates might play a role in PIH.	Very low +/++++
Wu et al. (2021)/USA	To examine the relationship between maternal phthalate exposure and maternal BP during pregnancy	Cohort study (PROGRESS study)	N = 892 pregnant women (enrolled during the second trimester, before 20 WG)	Urinary samples collected at T2 and T3 for 15 phthalate metabolites quantification, BP determination at T2 and T3	High concentrations of MEP and MCPP at T1, and MiBP at T3 are associated with PIH (OR 1.4, CI 1.09–1.79, p = 0.01 and OR 1.34, CI 1.05–1.7, p = 0.02; for MEP and MCPP, respectively and OR 1.5, CI 1.01–2.22, p = 0.04 for MiBP). MBP, MEP and Σ DEHP urinary concentrations at T1 were associated with increased sBP at T3 (β = 1.65, CI 0.3–2.99, p = 0.02; β 0.96, CI 0.11–1.8, p = 0.03; and β = 1.52, CI 0.17–2.86, p = 0.03, respectively).	Maternal urinary phthalate concentrations were associated with higher BP during mid-to-late pregnancy.	Very low +/++++
Bedell et al. (2021)/USA	To evaluate the association between maternal urinary phthalate metabolite concentration and PIH	Prospective cohort study	N = 668 pregnant women (before 13rd WG)	PIH (gestational hypertension, preeclampsia, eclampsia and HELLP syndrome) at T1 and T3. Phthalate quantification in urine samples.	MCPP at 16 weeks positively associated with sBP (β = 2.1 mm Hg, 95 % CI 0.2, 4.1) No relationship with PIH.	Several phthalate metabolites were associated with PIH and increased sBP along the pregnancy.	Low ++/++++
Vuong et al. (2021)/USA	To estimate associations between phthalates and changes in BP	Cohort study	N = 468 pregnant women	sBP, dBP and phthalate determination in maternal serum and urine at 16 and 26 WG	High exposure to DMP (OR = 1.56 (95 % CI: 0.78, 2.35)), DEP (OR = 1.09 (OR = 0.37, 1.81)), DBP (OR = 4.45 (95 % CI: 3.66, 5.23)) at T1 was associated with high	No consistent association between phthalates and PIH	Very low +/++++
Gao et al. (2021)/ China	To evaluate the association between phthalate exposure and BP among pregnant women	Cohort study	N = 3473 pregnant women before 13 WG	Maternal BP, single phthalate diester quantification in urine and serum samples in each visit until birth	High exposure to DMP (OR = 1.56 (95 % CI: 0.78, 2.35)), DEP (OR = 1.09 (OR = 0.37, 1.81)), DBP (OR = 4.45 (95 % CI: 3.66, 5.23)) at T1 was associated with high	Phthalate exposure at T1 is associated with increased risk of HDOP	Very low +/++++

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Table 3 (continued)

Author(s) (year)/country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
Han et al. (2020)/China	To assess the association between phthalate concentration in urine and BP in pregnancy	Cohort study	N = 636 pregnant women	Urine samples at T1-T3 for determination of 9 phthalate metabolites and BP measurements.	sBP at T3 (HI OR = 5.22 (95 % CI: 4.29, 6.15)) dBP at T2 was positively associated to MiBP (adjusted β = 0.76, 95 % CI: 0.24, 1.28, P-FDR = 0.05) and Σ LMW (adjusted β = 1.07, 95 % CI: 0.30, 1.83, P-FDR = 0.05) at T1 in women carrying male fetuses.	Exposure to MiBP may be associated with increased BP in pregnant women with male fetuses, but not met the threshold for HDOP.	Very low +/++++
Warembourg et al. (2019)/Europe	To study the impact of phthalates on BP among pregnant women.	Cohort study	N = 152 volunteer pregnant women in the HELIX project (n = 52 from Barcelona (Spain), n = 46 from Grenoble (France) and n = 55 from Oslo (Norway)) before week 20 of pregnancy	Urine collection for 10 phthalate metabolites analysis at around 18 and 32 WG and BP measurement	Decrease in sBP was observed with increasing levels of MEP (β = -0.91 mm Hg, 95 % CI: -1.44, -0.07). MiBP produce a decrease in sBP only at T2 (β = -2.14 mm Hg, 95 % CI: -4.02, -0.25)	Phthalates exposure is associated with lower sBP during pregnancy.	Very low +/++++
Philips et al. (2019)/Netherlands	To evaluate the relationship between phthalates exposure and the risk of GHD	Cohort study	N = 1396 women recruited in the early pregnancy	Phthalate metabolite concentrations in urine samples and BP measurements in early pregnancy (12.1–14.5 WG)	No association between phthalate metabolites and sBP during pregnancy. DNOP metabolites were associated with lower dBP (-0.80 mm Hg; 95 % CI: -1.52, -0.07)	Phthalate metabolites were not associated with changes in BP values during pregnancy	Low +/++++
Cantonwine et al. (2016)/USA	To analyze the relationship between phthalate metabolite concentrations and preeclampsia	Nested case-control study (birth cohort study at Brigham and Women's Hospital in Boston)	N = 50 cases (preeclampsia) and 431 controls	Maternal spot urine samples at 4.7–16.1, 14.9–21.9, 22.9–29.3 and 33.1–38.3 WG for quantification of 9 phthalate metabolites (MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, MBzP, MBP, MiBP, MEP and MCPP); blood pressure and urinary protein testing or protein/creatinine ratio measurement.	IQR increase of urinary MEP at 10 WG (1.72; 95 % CI: 1.28, 2.30) was associated with onset of preeclampsia Significantly elevated HR across gestation for Σ DEHP metabolites (HR: 2.10 (95 % CI: 1.44, 3.07))	Urinary increased concentrations of MEP and Σ DEHP were associated with onset of preeclampsia	Very low +/++++
Werner et al. (2015)/USA	To evaluate the association between urinary phthalate metabolites and PIH.	Prospective birth cohort study	N = 369 low-risk pregnant women	Urinary samples at 16 and 26 WG for determination of Σ DEHP, Σ DBP, MEP, MCPP and MBzP. Maternal BP at <20 and \geq 20 WG and diagnosis of PIH.	MBzP concentrations in the 3rd tertile at 16 WG were associated with dBP 2.2 (95 % CI: 0.5–3.9) mm Hg higher at <20 WG and 2.8 (95 % CI: 0.9–4.7) mm Hg higher at \geq 20 WG, and increased risk of PIH disorders (RR = 2.92, 95 % CI 1.15–7.41, p = 0.01). MBzP concentrations at 26 WG were no associated with increased BP or PIH disorders.	Maternal urinary increased MBzP concentrations were associated with increased dBP and PIH disorders.	Low +/++++
Ferguson et al. (2015a)/USA	To study the relationship between plasma biomarkers of angiogenesis and urinary phthalate concentrations.	Nested case-control study	N = 582 (130 preterm births and 352 term births)	Determination of plasmatic PlGF and sFlt-1 concentrations, and 9 urinary phthalate metabolites (MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, MBzP, MBP, MiBP, MEP, MCPP) at 10, 18, 26 and 35 WG	DEHP urinary concentrations were associated with decrease in PlGF (p = 0.029) and increase in sFlt-1/PlGF ratio (p = 0.020)	DEHP exposure may be related with disorders in placental function during pregnancy	Very low +/++++

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Table 3 (continued)

Author(s) (year)/ country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
LaRocca et al. (2014)/USA	To evaluate the impact of phthalate exposure on IGF2/H19 genomic imprinting and PIH disorders	Cohort study	N = 196 pregnant women from the Predictors of Preeclampsia Study and the Harvard Epigenetic Birth Cohort	Determination of urinary concentration of 11 phthalate metabolites at T1, study of H19 and IGF2 placental methylation	LMW phthalate and Σ phthalate concentrations were inversely associated with H19 ($p < 0.05$) and IGF2DMR0 ($p < 0.05$) placental methylation values. No association with PIH disorders was found.	Maternal exposure to phthalates may produce placental methylation disorders of the imprinting H19 and IGF2DMR0 genes. No association with PIH disorders were found.	Very low +/++++

Abbreviations. BP: blood pressure; dBp: diastolic blood pressure; DBP: dibutyl phthalate; DEHP: di-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate; DEP: diethyl phthalate; DMP: dimethyl phthalate; DNOP: di-n-octylphthalate; GHD: gestational hypertensive disorders; HDOP: hypertensive disorders of pregnancy; HI: hazard index; HOME: Health Outcomes and Measures of the Environment; HPLC-MS/MS: high performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry; HR: hazard ratio; IQR: interquartile range; LMW: low molecular weight; MBP: mono-n-butyl phthalate; MBzP: mono-benzyl phthalate; MCNP: monocarboxy-isobutyl phthalate; MCOP: monocarboxy-isooctyl phthalate; MCP: mono-3-carboxypropyl phthalate; MECPP: mono(2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) phthalate; MEHHP: mono(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate; MEHP: mono(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate; MEOHP: mono(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate; MEP: monoethyl phthalate; MiBP: monoisobutyl phthalate; MMP: mono-methyl phthalate; MNP: mono-isobutyl phthalate; PIH: pregnancy-induced hypertension; PIGF: placental growth factor; PROGRESS: Programing Research in Obesity, Growth, Environment and Social Stressors; sBP: systolic blood pressure; Sft-1: soluble fms-like tyrosine kinase-1; WG: weeks of gestation. Quality of evidence grades: high (++++), moderate (+++), low (++) , very low (+).

found a positive association between maternal exposure to MECPP (Zhu et al., 2018), MEOHP (Zhu et al., 2018), Σ DEHP (Zhu et al., 2018), MCOP (Sathyanarayana et al., 2016), DEHP (Sathyanarayana et al., 2016), MBzP (Casas et al., 2016) and fetal growth. Interestingly, all three studies (Zhu et al., 2018; Sathyanarayana et al., 2016; Casas et al., 2016) found differences only in full-term newborn boys, but not in full-term newborn girls. Only the study conducted by Sathyanarayana et al. found an increase of 0.49 kg in preterm girls (Sathyanarayana et al., 2016). These sex-specific differences could be explained by estrogenic (Li et al., 2021) or antiandrogenic effects of phthalates (Zhu et al., 2018; Li et al., 2021). In addition, six studies found no association between phthalate exposure during fetal development and differences in fetal growth (LaRocca et al., 2014; Stevens et al., 2022; Lee et al., 2020; Maekawa et al., 2017; Govarts et al., 2016; Cowell et al., 2023). When these studies were analyzed in depth, most of them presented small cohorts (LaRocca et al., 2014; Maekawa et al., 2017; Govarts et al., 2016) or a small group of FGR fetuses (Govarts et al., 2016), or analyzed a reduced number of phthalate metabolites (Lee et al., 2020; Cowell et al., 2023). Stevens et al. also found an increased risk of low birth weight in neonates prenatally exposed to phthalates, but the differences were not statistically significant (Stevens et al., 2022). In all these cases, increasing the sample size or analyzing a larger number of metabolites may have contributed to the differences in fetal growth.

In relation to the timing of phthalate exposure, the reviewed studies showed great heterogeneity with regard to the trimester of analysis and the matrix used for phthalate quantification. Most studies analyzed phthalate exposure in urine samples (Zhao et al., 2015, 2014, 2016; LaRocca et al., 2014; Santos et al., 2021; Ferguson et al., 2016; Bloom et al., 2019; Bommarito et al., 2021; Zang et al., 2023; Hu et al., 2021; Stevens et al., 2023a, 2022; Zhu et al., 2018; Sathyanarayana et al., 2016; Casas et al., 2016; Li et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2020; Maekawa et al., 2017; Cowell et al., 2023), five of them in the 3 trimesters of pregnancy (Santos et al., 2021; Ferguson et al., 2016; Li et al., 2021; Stevens et al., 2022; Cowell et al., 2023), five studies in early pregnancy (LaRocca et al., 2014; Hu et al., 2021; Sathyanarayana et al., 2016; Casas et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2020), and seven studies in late pregnancy or at birth (Zhao et al., 2015, 2014, 2016; Bommarito et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2018; Casas et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2020; Maekawa et al., 2017). However, other studies evaluated phthalate exposure in maternal blood (Guo et al., 2022; Miura et al., 2021; Lenters et al., 2016) or umbilical cord blood (Huang et al., 2014; Govarts et al., 2016) at birth. Phthalates have a short half-life, representing exposure for up to three months (Santos

et al., 2021), so the timing of phthalate quantification is important when interpreting fetal growth results. Evidence suggests that fetal development is most vulnerable to endocrine disruptors in early pregnancy (Zang et al., 2023; Shirangi et al., 2020). However, studies in early pregnancy do not allow evaluation of the cumulative effects of phthalates on fetal development at different stages of pregnancy, so we need to be careful when evaluating the effects of phthalates on fetal growth depending on the time of exposure, without forgetting the effects of other EDCs that share similar sources of exposure with phthalates.

Several pathophysiological mechanisms have been defined to explain the effect of prenatal phthalate exposure on fetal growth (Fig. 3), specifically changes in DNA methylation (Zhao et al., 2015, 2016; LaRocca et al., 2014; Miura et al., 2021), proinflammatory effects through PPARs or induction of (COX-2) expression (Stevens et al., 2022), thyroid and hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis disruption (Miura et al., 2021; Bloom et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2018; Zhong et al., 2021), placental abnormalities via fatty acids imbalance, oxidative stress-mediated DNA damage or alterations in placental thyroid hormone receptor signaling (Santos et al., 2021; Bloom et al., 2019), renin and cortisol secretion disorders (Miura et al., 2021; Bloom et al., 2019), estrogenic and antiandrogenic effects (Bloom et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2018; Zhong et al., 2021) and oxidative stress induction (Zhao et al., 2015, 2016; Sathyanarayana et al., 2016; Cowell et al., 2023).

3.5. Preterm birth

Several studies have investigated the effect of phthalate exposure during pregnancy on PTB (<37 weeks of pregnancy) and gestational age. Thirty-four studies from the last 10 years that reported outcomes of PTB and gestational age were included. The main findings are described in Table 5.

Four meta-analyses evaluated maternal exposure to phthalates with PTB. In 2022, Wu Y. et al. included 59 studies and reported an increased risk for PTB, especially for exposure to MEP, MECPP, MBzP, and DEHP (Wu et al., 2022). In the same year, based on 7 prospective studies, Wang X. et al. (Wang et al., 2022) reported that MBP, Σ DEHP, and MCP: were significantly correlated with the risk of PTB. Spontaneous preterm birth (sPTB) was associated with higher urinary levels of MEP, MCP: and MiBP, and MBP. However, Zhong et al. (Zhong et al., 2021) suggested a positive association but not statistically significant association, which the authors explained by the considerable heterogeneity of the included studies. More recently, based on seventeen studies, Liu B. et al. reported

Table 4

Summary of studies based on the association between prenatal phthalate exposure and fetal growth.

Author(s) (year)/country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
Stevens et al. (2023a)/USA	To assess associations between biomarkers of phthalate exposure in midpregnancy and infant size and body composition	Cohort study	N = 438 infants (Healthy Start prospective pregnancy cohort)	16 phthalate metabolite (MEP, MBzP, MCP, MCOP, MCNP, MnBP, MHBP, MiBP, MHiBP, MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, and Σ DEHP) measurement in urine samples collected at 24–28 WG. Weight and body composition at birth.	MBzP [−45 (95 % CI: −79, −12)] and Σ DBP [−59 (95 % CI: −100, −14)] were inversely associated with birthweight. MBzP [−0:49 (95 % CI: −0:91, −0:08)] and Σ DBP [−0.51 (95 % CI: −1:02, 0.01)] were inversely associated with percentage fat mass at birth among males. No association was found in females.	Phthalate exposure in midpregnancy was associated with lower birthweight and fat mass.	Very low +/++++
Zang et al. (2023)/China	To assess the association between prenatal phthalate exposure and LBW	Cohort study	N = 1484 pregnant women (Jiangsu Birth Cohort)	17 phthalate metabolite (MMP, MEP, MiBP, MHiBP, MnBP, MHBP, MCP, MBzP, MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, MCMHP, MiNP, MCOP, oxo_MiNP, and oh_MiNP) quantification in urine samples before 14 WG. Birth weight.	Prenatal exposure to MEP (RR = 1.27; 95 % CI: 1.03, 1.56) and MCOP (RR = 1.31; 95 % CI: 1.03, 1.67) were positively associated with LBW in ART-conceived babies. Prenatal exposure to MCMHP (RR = 0.56; 95 % CI: 0.36, 0.87) were positively associated with LBW in spontaneously-conceived babies.	Prenatal exposure to phthalates was associated with increased risk of LBW.	Low ++/++++
Cowell et al. (2023)/USA	To investigate the association between maternal phthalate exposure and fetal growth	Cohort study	N = 855 mother-fetal pairs (New York University Children's Health and Environment Study)	Σ DEHP, Σ DnOP, Σ DiNP urine determination at T1-T3 by HPLC-ESI-MS/MS. EFW at 20, 30 and 36 WG	Σ DiNP was associated with −31.3 g in EFW (95 % CI: −69.4-6.8) at the 10th percentile for females and +10.3 g in EFW (95 % CI: −14.8-35.3) at the 10th percentile for males. Σ DiNP was associated with +37.7 g in EFW (95 % CI: 3.0-72.4) at the 90th percentile for females and −24.0 g in EFW (95 % CI: −60.4-30.5) at the 90th percentile for males.	Phthalates are associated with small sex specific differences in fetal growth.	Very low +/++++
Stevens et al. (2022)/USA	To evaluate the association between maternal phthalate exposure and FGR	Prospective cohort study	N = 604 singleton pregnancies (<13 WG) from TIDES cohort (2010–2012)	MEP, MBzP, MnBP, MiBP, MCP, MCNP, MCOP, MEHP, MEOHP, MEHHP and MECPP determination in spot urinary samples in each trimester, fetal biometrics at T2 and T3, birthweight and length	A one-quartile increase in the phthalate mixture was associated with reduced birthweight (β [95 % confidence interval]: −54.6 [−128.9–19.7] grams; $p = 0.15$) and length (−0.2 [−0.6–0.2] centimeters; $p = 0.40$). MBzP was the major contributor to the inverse association between prenatal exposure and fetal growth	Maternal phthalate exposure was not significantly associated with fetal growth	Low ++/++++
Guo et al. (2022)/China	To examine the association between prenatal phthalate exposure and FGR	Nested case-control study	N = 97 FGR neonates and 291 matched controls from Guangxi Zhuang Birth Cohort. Pregnant women	BBP, DBP, DEHP, DEP, DMP, MBP, MEHP phthalate determination in maternal serum before 22 WG by GC-MS. Determination of FGR	BBP (OR = 1.849, 95 % CI: 1.080–3.177, $p = 0.025$), DEHP (OR = 3.893, 95 % CI: 1.305–11.910, $p = 0.015$) and DMP (OR = 1.722, 95 % CI:	Maternal exposure to BBP, DEHP and DMP in early pregnancy increased the risk of FGR.	Low ++/++++

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Table 4 (continued)

Author(s) (year)/country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
			recruitment ≤ 22 WG	according to birth weight and gestational age	1.089–2.725, $p = 0.020$) were significantly positively associated with FGR. MBP (OR = 1.722, 95 % CI: 1.089–2.725, $p = 0.020$) were significantly negatively associated with FGR in girls.		
Li et al. (2021)/China	To assess the trimester-specific and sex-specific impact of prenatal DEHP exposure on fetal growth	Prospective cohort study	N = 814 mother-offspring pairs	Urine samples at 13.1 \pm 1.22 WG, 23.6 \pm 3.31 WG and 35.9 \pm 3.36 WG. DEHP quantification using LC-MS-MS. EFW using Hadlock algorithm	Males: negative association between DEHP with fetal growth at T1 ($\beta < 0$, $p < 0.05$), negative association between DEHP to birth weight at T2 ($\beta < 0$, $p < 0.05$), positive association between DEHP with birth weight at T3 ($\beta > 0$, $p < 0.05$). Females: no association between DEHP with fetal growth or birth weight differences.	Prenatal DEHP exposure at T1 and T2 was associated with decreased fetal growth and birth weight. There are sex-specific differences.	Very low +/++++
Hu et al. (2021)/Canada	To investigate the relationship between maternal phthalate exposure and fetal growth.	Cohort study (Maternal-Infant Research on Environmental Chemicals Study)	N = 1857 pregnant women recruited at T1	MCPP, MBzP, MEP, MnBP and Σ DEHP urinary determination at T1 and birth weight.	MCPP -14.8 g (-28.1 , -1.5 %) and Σ DEHP -13 g (-29.3 , -3.3) decreased birth weight.	Maternal phthalate exposure was associated with reduction in birth weight.	Low ++/++++
Bommarito et al. (2021)/USA	To study the association between maternal phthalate exposure and FGR.	Nested case-control study (LIFESCODES study)	SGA = 31, control = 31, LGA = 28 Recruitment before 15 WG.	MEP, MBP, MBzP, MiBP, MECPP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MEHP, MCPP, MCOP and MCNP urine quantification at 26 and 35 GW and EFW.	MEP was associated with reduction in LGA fetuses (OR 0.33 (0.14–0.78))	Phthalate maternal exposure was associated with a reduction in LGA fetuses.	Low ++/++++
Santos et al. (2021)/Netherlands	To evaluate the association between maternal phthalate exposure and fetal growth	Prospective cohort study	N = 1379 pregnant women	Urinary LMWP, HMWP, DEHP and DNOP metabolite determination at T1-T3. EFW using Hadlock algorithm	Phthalic acid (SD = 0.17 (95 % CI:0.05–0.30) $p = 0.001$), LMWP (SD = 0.18 (95 % CI:0.05–0.31) $p = 0.002$), HMWP (SD = 0.11 (95 % CI:0.00–0.22) $p = 0.04$) and DEHP (SD = 0.11 (95 % CI:0.00–0.22) $p = 0.05$) were associated with lower EFW	Maternal exposure to high concentrations of phthalates is associated with FGR	Low ++/++++
Miura et al. (2021)/Japan	To study the association of DEHP prenatal exposure with DNA methylation changes and offspring's PI	Retrospective cohort study (Sapporo cohort of the Hokkaido Study on Environment and Children's Health)	N = 514 mother-child pairs	Maternal blood MEHP metabolite analysis using GC-MS. Measurement of DNA methylation at 485,577 CpGs in cord blood.	203 mother-child pairs with detectable MEHP levels. 2 CpGs with significant methylation alteration (FDR q -value <0.05) MEPH positive association with methylation levels. Methylation levels at cg27433759:PIK3CG, cg10548708:ACAA1, and cg07002201: FUT9 were inversely related to the offspring's PI ($p < 0.1$)	Prenatal DEHP exposure is associated with DNA methylation changes and FGR.	Very low +/++++
Shirangi et al. (2020)/Australia	To analyze the effects of prenatal occupational	Prospective birth cohort study (Born in Bradford Study)	N = 4142 pregnant women	Mid-pregnancy questionnaire (26–28 WG) about employment status	POBW <85 increased in mothers exposed to phthalates (RR _{adj} 3.71, 95 % CI	Prenatal exposure to phthalates is associated with FGR	Low ++/++++

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Table 4 (continued)

Author(s) (year)/country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
	exposure on the risk of FGR.			linked to JEM for EDC exposure. SGA and POBW data collection.	1.62–8.51) Phthalates exposure statistically non-significantly increased in SGA fetuses (RR _{adj} 1.69, 95 % CI 0.34–8.41, p = 0.52). No association between early or late prenatal exposure to MEHHP, MEOHP, MnBP and birth weight.		
Lee et al. (2020)/ Republic of Korea	To assess the effects of maternal exposure to phthalates on birth weight.	Prospective birth cohort (The mothers and Children's Environmental Health study)	N = 719 mother-child pairs.	Determination of MEHHP, MEOHP and MnBP in maternal urine samples during early pregnancy (12–20 WG) and late pregnancy (28–42 WG)	MiBP (OR = 2.82; 95 % CI: 1.21–6.56) and MEOHP (OR = 2.80; 95 % CI: 1.05–7.42) were associated with higher SGA risk. MEP (OR = 1.33; 95 % CI: 0.95–1.86) was associated with higher LBW risk.	Maternal exposure to phthalates is not associated with FGR.	Low ++/++++
Bloom et al. (2019)/USA	To study the association between maternal urinary phthalate metabolites and fetal growth	Prospective mother-infant birth cohort study	N = 310 pregnant women recruited between 18 and 22 WG	Measurement of MEHP, MEOHP, MEHHP, MEP, MMP, ΣDEHP and ΣDBP in maternal urine samples. Birth weight, SGA and LBW < 2500 g.	MECPP was associated with 59.8 g increased birth weight (95 % CI: 19.8–99.9), MEOHP 42.2 g (95 % CI: 1.2–83.3), and ΣDEHP 47.7 g (95 % CI: 3.1–92.3) in boys. MECP was associated with a 0.23 kg/m ³ increased ponderal index in boys (95 % CI: 0.03–0.47). No significant association between maternal phthalate exposure and birth size in girls.	Phthalate exposure in pregnancy is associated with FGR	Low ++/++++
Zhu et al. (2018)/China	To evaluate the relationship between phthalate prenatal exposure and birth size	Prospective cohort study (Healthy Birth Cohort)	N = 1002 mother-infant pairs	MMP, MEP, MBP, MEHP, MECP, MEHHP and MEOHP determination in urine samples before delivery by SPE-UPLC-MS/MS. Birth weight, birth length, birth weight Z-scores and ponderal index measurements.	MECPP was associated with a 0.23 kg/m ³ increased ponderal index in boys (95 % CI: 0.03–0.47). No significant association between maternal phthalate exposure and birth size in girls.	DEHP metabolites were positively associated with birth weight and ponderal index in boys, but no significant associations were found in girls.	Very low +/++++
Maekawa et al. (2017)/Japan	To investigate the relationship between FGR and prenatal phthalate exposure.	Prospective cohort study	N = 145 pregnant women recruited at admission for labor (37–42 WG)	MEHP and DEHP determination in blood and urine samples, amniotic fluid, and cord blood.	Prenatal DEHP and MEHP exposure were not significantly associated to FGR.	Japanese women are exposed to phthalates, but no association with FGR was found.	Very low +/++++
Zhao et al. (2016)/China	To study association between maternal phthalate exposure and DNA methylation in human placenta.	Case-control study	N = 181 mother newborn pairs (80 FGR and 101 controls)	urinary MEHHP and MEOHP phthalate metabolite concentrations at T3 and placental DNA methylation levels of IGF2 and AHRR.	MEHHP was associated with 2.95 % (position 1: β = -2.953, p = 0.005) and 3.92 % (position 2: β = -3.923, p = 0.039) decrease in IGF2 methylation. MEOHP was associated with 2.88 % (position 1: β = -2.879, p = 0.004) and 4.52 % (position 2: β = -4.518, p = 0.013) decrease in IGF2 methylation. MEHHP and MEOHP were inversely associated with DNA methylation at position 1 of IGF2 in FGR newborns.	Maternal phthalate exposure is associated with placental DNA methylation and FGR.	Low ++/++++
Ferguson et al. (2016)/USA	To determine the effect of maternal phthalate exposure on fetal growth.	Prospective cohort study	N = 482 singleton pregnancies recruited before 15 WG	DEHP, MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP and MECP determination in spot urine samples at 10, 18, 26 and 35 WG. EFW measurement by ultrasound scan.	DEHP was associated with 0.13 SD decrease in EFW (95 % CI: -0.23, -0.03), MECP -0.13 SD (95 % CI: -0.22, -0.03) and MEOHP -0.10 SD	Prenatal DEHP exposure was associated with FGR.	Very low +/++++

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Table 4 (continued)

Author(s) (year)/country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
Lenters et al. (2016)/Netherlands	To evaluate the association between maternal phthalate exposure and birth weight.	Prospective cohort study	N = 1250 singleton pregnancies	DEHP and DiNP maternal serum determinations and term birth weight measurement	(95 % CI: -0.20, -0.01) MEHHP was associated with -87 g birth weight (95 % CI: -137, -340 per 170 ng/mL)	Maternal MEHHP exposure was associated with impaired fetal growth.	Low ++/++++
Sathyanarayana et al. (2016)/USA	To assess the association between phthalate exposure at T1 and birth weight	Prospective cohort study (The Infant Development and the Environment Study)	N = 753 pregnant women recruited before 13 WG	MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, ΣDEHP, MEP, MBzP, MBP, MCPP and MCOP urinary phthalate determination at T1 by HPLC-ESI-MS/MS and birth weight measurement.	MCOP positively associated with birth weight (0.13 kg, 95 % CI 0.03-0.23) in term males. DEHP positively associated with birth weight (0.49 kg, 95 % CI 0.09-0.89) in preterm females.	Maternal phthalate exposure was positively associated with fetal growth in term and preterm births.	Very low +/++++
Casas et al. (2016)/Spain	To examine phthalate prenatal exposure association with fetal growth.	Prospective cohort study (INfancia y MEdioambiente study)	N = 488 mother-child pairs recruited before 16 WG	Urine phthalate quantification in at T1 and T3. EFW at 12-20 and 20-34 WG, and birth weight.	MBzP positively associated with birth weight (48 g; 95 % CI: 6-90) in boys, but not in girls.	There is weak evidence for MBzP positively association with birth weight.	Very low +/++++
Govarts et al. (2016)/Belgium	To analyze the effect of phthalate exposure on birth weight.	Cohort study (Flemish human environmental health survey II mother-child cohort)	N = 248 singleton pregnancies	MECPP, MEHHP, MEOHP determination in cord plasma at birth. Birth weight measurement.	No statistically significant association between DEHP metabolites and birth weight	Prenatal DEHP exposure has no effect on fetal weight.	Very low +/++++
Zhao et al. (2015)/China	To study the association between maternal phthalate exposure, FGR and placental DNA methylation	Case-control study	N = 119 mother-infant pairs (55 FGR and 64 controls)	Urinary maternal MBP, MMP, MEHP, MEOHP and MEHHP, quantification in by HPLC at T3. EFW by ultrasound scan. Placental LINE-1 methylation by PCR-pyrosequencing.	MEHP (p = 0.02), MEOHP (p = 0.03) and ΣDEHP (p = 0.02) were higher in FGR cases. Increase in urinary concentrations of MEHHP and ΣDEHP was associated with 0.015 kg (β = -0.015, p = 0.015) and 0.012 kg (β = -0.012, p = 0.167) decrease in birth weight mediated through LINE-1 methylation.	Reduction in placental LINE-1 methylation could be related to the underlying molecular pathway between maternal phthalate exposure and FGR.	Low ++/++++
LaRocca et al. (2014)/USA	To estimate the impact of phthalate exposure on IGF2/H19 genomic imprinting and FGR	Cohort study (Predictors of Preeclampsia Study and the Harvard Epigenetic Birth Cohort)	N = 196 pregnant women	Determination of urinary concentration of 11 phthalate metabolites at T1, study of H19 and IGF2 placental methylation	LMW phthalate and Σphthalate concentrations were inversely associated with H19 (p < 0.05) and IGF2DMR0 (p < 0.05) placental methylation values. No association with FGR was found.	Maternal exposure to phthalates may produce placental methylation disorders of the imprinting H19 and IGF2DMR0 genes, but no association with FGR was found.	Very low +/++++
Huang et al. (2014)/China	To evaluate the relationship between prenatal phthalate exposure and fetal growth.	Cohort study	N = 207 women recruited at birth	DMP, DEP, DIBP, DBP, DMEP, BMPP, DEEP, DPP, DNHP, BBP, DBEP, DCHP, DEHP, DNOP and DNP phthalate determination in umbilical cord blood by GC/MS. Birth weight and birth length measurements.	DMEP was associated with 143 g (95 % CI -273, -14) decreased in birth weight in females (p < 0.05). DPP and DBEP were associated with 1.92 cm (95 % CI -3.49, -0.36) and 0.30 cm (95 % CI -0.54, -0.05), respectively decreased birth length in males (p < 0.05).	DMEP was associated with birth weight, and DPP and DBEP were associated with length. Sex specific differences were found.	Very low +/++++
Zhao et al. (2014)/China	To assess the association between maternal phthalate exposure with risk of FGR.	Case-control study	N = 126 mother newborn pairs (42 FGR and 84 controls)	MBP, MMP, MEHP, MEOHP and MEHHP determination in spot urine samples at T3. EFW by ultrasound scan	MMP (p = 0.030), MEHHP (p = 0.003), MEOHP (p = 0.003) and ΣDEHP (p = 0.004) were associated with FGR. MEHHP and MEOHP were associated with	Gestational exposure to phthalates was associated with increased risk of FGR. Sex differences were found.	Low ++/++++

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Table 4 (continued)

Author(s) (year)/ country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
					FGR in boys ($p < 0.05$), but not in girls.		

Abbreviations. AHRR: aryl hydrocarbon receptor repressor; BBP: butyl-benzyl phthalate; BMPP: bis (4-methyl-2-pentyl) phthalate; DBEP: bis (2-nbutoxyethyl) phthalate; DBP: di-n-butyl phthalate; DCHP: dicyclohexyl phthalate; DEEP: bis (2-ethoxyethyl) phthalate; DEHP: di (2-ethyl-hexyl) phthalate; DEP: di (2-ethyl) phthalate; DiBP: diisobutyl phthalate; DiNP: diisononyl phthalates; DMEP: bis (2-methoxyethyl) phthalate; DMP: dimethyl phthalate; DNHP: dihexyl phthalate; DnOP: di-n-octylphthalate; DNP: dinonyl phthalate; DPP: diamyl phthalate; EDC: endocrine disrupting chemicals; EFW: estimated fetal weight; FGR: fetal growth restriction; GC-MS: gas chromatography-mass spectrometry; HMWP: high-molecular-weight phthalates; HPLC: high performance liquid chromatography; HPLC-ESI-MS/MS: High Performance Liquid Chromatography - Electrospray Tandem Mass Spectrometry; JEM: job exposure matrix; LBW: low birth weight; LC-MS-MS: liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry; LGA: large for gestational age; LINE-1: long interposed nuclear element-1; LMWP: low-molecular weight phthalates; MBP: mono-butyl phthalate; MBzP: mono-benzyl phthalate; MCMHP: mono(2-carboxymethylhexyl) phthalate; MCNP: mono-carboxy-isononyl phthalate; MCP: mono-carboxy-isooctyl phthalate; MCP: mono-3-carboxy-propyl phthalate; MECPP: mono-2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl phthalate; MEHHP: mono-2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl phthalate; MEHP: mono-2-ethylhexyl phthalate; MEOHP: mono-2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl phthalate; MEP: mono-ethyl phthalate; MiBP: mono-isobutyl phthalate; MMP: monomethyl phthalate; MnBP: mono-n-butyl phthalate; oh_MiNP: monohydroxyisononyl phthalate; OR: odds ratio; PI: ponderal index; POBW: percentage of optimal birth weight; RRadj: adjusted risk ratio; SD: standard deviation; SGA: small for gestational age; SPE-UPLC-MS/MS: ultraperformance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry; T1: first trimester; T2: second trimester; T3: third trimester; TIDES: The Infant Development and Environment study; WG: weeks of gestation. Quality of evidence grades: high (++++), moderate (+++), low (++) , very low (+).

a pooled odds ratio (OR) of PTB for maternal exposure to phthalates of 1.16 (95 % CI: 1.11–1.12), with maternal exposure to MECPP being significantly associated with PTB (OR 1.41, 95 % CI: 1.22–1.62) (Liu et al., 2024).

Several phthalate metabolites have been evaluated in relation to PTB. A negative association between the gestational age and maternal MEP in the third trimester was observed in a prospective cohort from Poland (Polańska et al., 2016). In addition, higher urinary concentrations of DEHP metabolites (MEHP, MECPP, and \sum DEHP) in pregnant women were also associated with a higher incidence of PTB (Boss et al., 2018; Ferguson et al., 2014a, 2014b; Welch et al., 2022), with a dose-dependent relationship (Ferguson et al., 2014a). In a cohort of sub-fertile couples, maternal \sum DEHP metabolite concentrations during pregnancy were also associated with an increased risk of PTB, especially in late pregnancy (Yland et al., 2022). Higher concentrations of specific LMWP, HMWP and DEHP metabolites have also been associated (Santos et al., 2021), and differences have also been reported according to the time of exposure. Moreover, MBP and metabolites of diisobutyl phthalate (DiBP), such as MiBP and mono-2-methyl-2-hydroxypropyl phthalate (MHiBP), have been associated with shorter gestation and more PTB (Ferguson et al., 2019a).

Phthalate metabolites have mostly been assessed in maternal urine samples. Only one study used umbilical cord blood as a matrix and found a reduction in gestational age and an increase in PTB rate (Huang et al., 2014).

Regarding the time of exposure, either during pregnancy or in the preconception period, both early and late pregnancy exposures increase the risk of preterm birth, although the mechanisms may be different (Ferguson et al., 2014b). Urinary \sum DEHP levels in the third trimester were associated with PTB (Ferguson et al., 2019b), as was orthophthalate (OR of 1.36 (95 % CI: 1.06–1.76)), mainly due to DEP (Broe et al., 2019). In the second trimester, a two-fold increase in MBP was associated with an increased risk of PTB (Sienas et al., 2022). In the first trimester, MEHP exposure has been suggested as the most important phthalate for PTB (22 %) (Y. Chen et al., 2022), although this association was not observed in the Canadian cohort (Hu et al., 2020). In the preconception period, exposure to selected phthalate plasticizers may be a potential risk factor for adverse pregnancy outcomes in subfertile couples, for both female and male fetuses (Y. Zhang et al., 2021).

In addition, the effects of maternal phthalate exposure on gestational age differed by race/ethnicity or fetal sex. The highest levels of DEP and other chemicals were found in non-Hispanic black women (Harris et al., 2022; Welch et al., 2023). When African American and white pregnant women were compared, it was found that African Americans had a higher PTB risk than whites for higher MiBP and MEP (Bloom et al., 2019) [OR = 2.03 (95 % CI: 0.85–4.83) vs. OR = 0.55 (95 % CI:

0.16–1.83), respectively], but a lower PTB risk than whites for higher MEHP.

With regard to fetal sex, most of the phthalate metabolites were significantly associated with an increased risk of late PTB in females but not in males (Bloom et al., 2019; Shoaff et al., 2016; Gao et al., 2019). However, a Canadian cohort study reported a higher risk of PTB in males (Hu et al., 2020) and Weinberger B et al. observed a 4.2 day reduction in gestational age only in males (Weinberger et al., 2014). Sex differences were also found in the PROTECT cohort, where women had a higher risk of PTB (Cathey et al., 2022a).

Currently, various mechanisms have been proposed to link phthalate exposure to preterm birth (Fig. 3), notably intrauterine inflammation and oxidative stress (Ferguson et al., 2017, 2015b, 2014c), hormonal disruption (Cathey et al., 2022b) and premature activation of the pro-labor genes (X.K. Wang et al., 2016).

3.6. Fetal neurodevelopment

To date, 19 studies have been conducted to determine the effect of prenatal exposure to phthalate metabolites on neurodevelopment in children, mostly analyzed at 3–4 years of age (Thomson et al., 2023; Rolland et al., 2023; Bornehag et al., 2018; Parenti et al., 2022; Choi et al., 2021; Alampi et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2021; Oulhote et al., 2020; Ponsonby et al., 2020; Torres-Olascoaga et al., 2020; Shin et al., 2018).

Although only one study followed children from 2 to 11 years of age (Ku et al., 2020), all studies detected phthalates in the urine samples collected, with percentages ranging from 80 % (Thomson et al., 2023) to 100 % of samples (Choi et al., 2021). A detailed summary of the main results, the population and the variables studied is given in Table 6.

The results showed that the parent phthalate DEHP (Thomson et al., 2023; Ponsonby et al., 2020; Torres-Olascoaga et al., 2020; Day et al., 2021), used in household products and medical devices, was present in maternal urine samples in all trimesters of pregnancy, demonstrating its effect in both sexes and at all ages tested (from 2 to 5 years). Torres-Olascoaga showed in 4-year-old children that its prenatal presence at T1 and T2 has a significant negative association with motor skills and motor scale, respectively, as well as with the DEHP metabolites MECPP, MEHHP and MEOHP (Torres-Olascoaga et al., 2020). The presence of prenatal DEHP at T3 also increased the odds ratios for autism spectrum disorder (ASD) traits in two-year-old children by up to 1.5 for each doubling of DEHP concentration in the samples (Ponsonby et al., 2020). Although the author did not elaborate on the possible underlying mechanisms, Thomson et al. found that DEHP upregulates maternal non-oxidative energy metabolism, increasing the likelihood of ASD symptoms in offspring. The authors concluded that the range of the estimated proportion of the effect of prenatal DEHP on ASD-related symptoms

Table 5
Summary of studies based on maternal exposure to phthalates and preterm birth.

Author(s) (year)/country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
Zhong et al. (2021)/ China	To synthesize the potential relation between prenatal exposure to phthalates and preterm birth and gestational age	Quantitative meta-analysis	20 articles	DEHP, DEP, DBP, BBP, DIBP and DINP, PTB, GA	Positive association of prenatal exposure to DHEP [OR = 1.1; 95 % CI: 0.89–1.4], DEP [OR = 1.1; 95 % CI: 0.92–1.3], DBP [OR = 1.1; 95 % CI: 0.77–1.4], BBP [OR = 1.0; 95 % CI: 0.91–1.2], DIBP [OR = 1.1; 95 % CI: 0.92–1.3], DINP [OR = 1.1; 95 % CI: 0.85–1.3] and PTB. Phthalates were negatively associated with GA except DHEP and DINP	Positive relation between prenatal phthalates exposure and PTB, and a negative association for GA	Moderate +++ /++++
Huang et al. (2014)/ China	To assess the relationship between 15 phthalate levels in cord blood and preterm delivery and fetal growth	Cohort	207 women	Cord blood metabolites (DEP, DNHP, BBP, DNP, DEEP)	Cord blood levels of all 15 phthalates predicted gestational age reduction and preterm delivery (except DCHP)	Prenatal exposure to phthalates is associated with younger gestational age and preterm delivery.	Low ++ /++++
Polańska et al. (2016)/ Poland	To evaluate the impact of phthalate exposure on pregnancy duration and birth outcomes based on the Polish Mother and Child Cohort (REPRO_PL)	Cohort	165 mothers	11 phthalate metabolites (MEP, MiBP, MnBP, MnBP, MBzP, MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MHiNP, MOiNP, and MOP) in urine	Pregnancy duration was inversely associated with natural log concentrations ($\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine) of MEP ($\beta = -0.2$, $p = 0.04$) after adjustment for a variety of confounders	Phthalate exposure may be associated with shorter pregnancy duration and a decreased head circumference.	Low ++ /++++
Boss et al. (2018)/USA	To find associations between gestational age at delivery with multiple phthalates	Nested case-control study	130 cases of PTB and 352 random controls	9 phthalate metabolites (MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, Σ DEHP, MBzP, MBP, MiBP, MEP, MCP)	The fourth quartile of ERS was significantly associated with a HR of 1.44 (95 % CI: 1.19–1.75) and a reduction of 2.55 % (95 % CI: 0.76–4.30 %) in time to delivery (in days) compared to the first quartile.	Pregnant women with higher urinary metabolite concentrations of individual phthalates have shorter time to delivery.	Moderate +++ /++++
Ferguson et al. (2014b)/ USA	To assess the relationship between phthalate exposure during pregnancy and preterm birth.	Nested case-control study	130 cases of PTB and 352 control participants	Levels of 9 phthalate exposure, spontaneous preterm birth	When spontaneous preterm births were examined alone, MEHP, MECPP, Σ DEHP, MBP, and MECPP levels were all associated with significantly elevated odds of prematurity.	Women exposed to phthalates during pregnancy have significantly increased odds of delivering preterm	Moderate +++ /++++
Ferguson et al. (2017)/USA	To examine variability in phthalate exposure across gestation and identify windows of susceptibility for the relationship with preterm birth	Nested case-control study	130 cases, as well as 352 random controls.	Urinary phthalate metabolite levels	Urinary phthalate metabolite levels were moderately variable over aOR for spontaneous preterm birth were strongest in association with phthalate metabolite concentrations measured at the beginning of T3 (aOR for Σ DEHP = 1.33, 95 % CI = 1.02–1.73)	Pregnant women with exposure to phthalates both early and late in Pregnancy are at an increased risk of delivering preterm, but mechanisms may differ based on etiology.	Low ++ /++++
Ferguson et al. (2019a)/ USA-Puerto Rico	To assess exposure to environmental contaminants as a contributing factor of preterm birth	Cohort study (PROTECT)	N = 1030	Urinary concentrations of metabolites of DBP and DiBP, MBP, MiBP	An IQR increases in MBP was associated with OR 1.42 (95 % CI: 1.07–1.88) for PTB. An IQR increases in DiBP was associated with OR of 1.32 (95 % CI: 1.02–1.71) for PTB.	Among pregnant women in the PROTECT cohort, DBP and DiBP metabolites were associated with increased OR of PTB.	Low ++ /++++
Ferguson et al. (2019b)/ USA	To study associations between phthalate exposure and PTB in mothers with higher stress in pregnancy	Cohort study (TIDES)	N = 783	Urinary phthalate metabolite concentrations measured in samples collected from up to three trimesters of pregnancy	Σ DEHP metabolites measured in urine samples at T3 were associated with an increased OR of PTB (OR = 1.44, 95 % CI = 1.06–1.95). In models stratified by SLE, associations between Σ DEHP concentrations at T3 and PTB were significant only for women	Association between urinary Σ DEHP levels and PTB was observed and that was modified by whether a mother was exposed to one or more psychosocial stressors during pregnancy.	Low ++ /++++

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Table 5 (continued)

Author(s) (year)/country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
Shoaff et al. (2016)/USA-Canada	To examine the relation between prenatal phthalate exposure and infant size at birth (birth weight z-score, length, and head circumference) and gestational duration	Cohort study (HOME)	N = 368	Phthalate metabolites in urine (ng/mL): MiBP, MBzP, MCP, MEHP, MECPP, MEHHP, MEOHP	experiencing one or more SLE during pregnancy (OR for Σ DEHP: 2.09, 95 % CI: 1.29–3.37) but not for women with no SLE during pregnancy. After covariate adjustment, phthalate metabolite concentrations were no longer associated with gestational duration.	In this cohort, urinary phthalate metabolites concentrations during pregnancy were not associated with gestational duration.	Low ++/++++
Weinberger et al. (2014)/USA	To study the association between maternal exposure to phthalates and BPA in gestational duration.	Cohort study	N = 72	Urinary phthalate and BPA metabolites, gender MEHP, MMP, MEP, MBP, MCHP, MEHHP, MDP, MEOHP, MOP, MNP, BPA total, BPA sulfate, and BPA glucuronide.	IQR increases in urinary MEHHP were associated with 4.2d decreases in gestation. These alterations were found only in male infants.	MEHHP and BPA are associated with reductions in gestation, with effects observed only in males	Low +/++++
Ferguson et al. (2017)/USA	To examine mediation of the association between phthalate exposure during pregnancy and preterm birth by oxidative stress	Nested case-control study	N = 130 cases, 352 controls	Phthalate metabolites: DHEP, MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP.	We observed mediation of the associations between phthalate metabolites and all PTB by 8-isoprostane (and for spontaneous PTB specifically)	This demonstrates mediation of the phthalate-preterm birth relationship by oxidative stress.	Moderate +++ /++++
Gao et al. (2019)/China	To explore the relationship of prenatal phthalate exposure with the risk of preterm birth and gestational age.	Prospective cohort	N = 3266 women	Seven phthalate metabolites (MMP, MEP, MBP, MBzP, MEHP, MEOHP, MEHHP)	Except for MMP (OR = 1.65, 95 % CI = 1.17–2.34), the average concentrations of phthalate metabolites were associated with a slightly and insignificantly increased risk of overall PTB.	Exposure to some phthalate metabolites was associated with increased risks of overall preterm birth and postterm birth.	Low ++/++++
Zhang et al. (2021b)/China	To study the joint effect of phenol and phthalate mixtures on preterm birth	Prospective cohort study	384 female and 211 male (203 couples)	Urinary concentrations of BPA, parabens, and eleven phthalate biomarkers, including DEHP metabolites	Maternal (aRR: 1.36, 95 % CI: 1.00–1.84) and paternal (aRR: 1.47, 95 % CI: 0.90–2.42) preconception DEHP-BPA factor was positively associated with PTB.	Maternal BPA and DEHP, and paternal DEHP exposure before conception were positively associated with PTB	Low ++/++++
Welch et al. (2022)/USA	To investigate the prospective association between urinary biomarkers of phthalates in pregnancy and PTB among individuals living in the US	Cohort study	6045 participants	Urinary phthalate metabolites	Higher OR of PTB, ranging from 12 % to 16 %, were observed in association with an interquartile range increase in urinary concentrations of MBP (OR = 1.12 [95 % CI, 0.98–1.27]), MiBP (OR = 1.16 [95 % CI, 1.00–1.34]), MECPP (OR = 1.16 [95 % CI, 1.00–1.34]), and MCP (OR = 1.14 [95 % CI, 1.01–1.29]).	Phthalate exposure during pregnancy may be a preventable risk factor for preterm delivery	Low ++/++++
Y. Chen et al. (2022)/China	To evaluate the associations of maternal EDCs mixture at T1–T3 with PTB, and identify the vital components that mainly contribute to PTB	Cohort study	847 pregnant women	Urine samples for all three trimesters of thirteen EDC metabolites (four phthalates)	Urinary EDCs mixture at T1 were positively associated with PTB [OR (95 % CI): 1.98 (1.10–3.58)], and the most heavily weighted component for PTB was BPA (26 %), followed by MEHP (22 %).	Exposure to higher EDCs mixture at T1 may increase the risk of PTB	Low ++/++++
Sienas et al. (2022)/USA	To study the association between prenatal phthalate exposure LPTB	CANDLE cohort (of the ECHO-PATHWAYS Consortium)	1408 women	14 phthalate metabolites	No association. In spontaneous PTL, second trimester MBP was associated with 54 % higher OR (95 % CI: 2 %, 132 %) of LPTB.	Secondary analyses suggest increased risk of spontaneous LPTB associated with MBP.	Very low +/++++
Wang et al. (2022)/China	To study the association between PTB and phthalate metabolites	Meta-analysis	7232 patients	11 phthalate metabolites and PTB, and 6 phthalate metabolites and spontaneous PTB	MBP, Σ DEHP and MCP significantly correlated with the risk of PTB (MBP: OR = 1.23, 95 % CI = 1.05–1.45; Σ DEHP: OR = 1.21, 95 % CI = 1.01–1.44; MCP: OR = 1.09, 95 %	MBP, Σ DEHP, and MCP levels are associated positively with PTB. MBP, MEP, MCP, and MiBP levels had increased OR for PTB	High ++++/++++

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Table 5 (continued)

Author(s) (year)/country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
Harris et al. (2022)/USA	To use available toxicogenomic data to identify chemical exposures that may contribute to PTB disparities	Cohort study	38,080 women	40 chemicals (including DEHP, DEP, DiBP)	CI = 1.00–1.19). PTB was associated with higher urinary levels of MEP, MCPP, MIBP, and MBP. PTB enriched chemicals that were detected at the highest levels in non-Hispanic Black women included DHEP.	Exposures to environmental chemicals contribute to racial disparities in PTB.	Very low + / + + + +
Cathey et al. (2022a)/USA	To investigate associations between phthalate metabolite mixtures and pregnancy outcomes	Cohort study (PROTECT)	462 females and 540 males	13 urinary phthalate metabolites	An IQ range increase in GA average phthalate ERS was associated with increased odds of PTB. Male OR = 1.56; 95 % CI: 1.08–2.27; female OR = 1.91; 95 % CI: 1.23, –2.98. PTB male OR = 2.32; 95 % CI: 1.46–3.68; female OR = 2.00; 95 % CI: 1.04–3.82.	Exposure to phthalate mixtures was associated with increased risk of early delivery. Highlight the need to study mixtures by fetal sex.	Low + + / + + + +
Yland et al. (2022)/USA	To study periods (preconception and prenatal exposure to phthalates) of heightened susceptibility during pregnancy.	Prospective cohort study	386 women undergoing fertility treatment who gave birth to a singleton infant during 2005 through 2018	11 phthalate metabolites (MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP; MEP, MBP, MiBP, MBzP, MCPP, MCOP, and MCNP) were measured in spot urine samples collected at study, two during fertility treatment and at each trimester of pregnancy.	RR of \sum DEHP in the third trimester (RR = 1.51; 95 % CI: 1.17–1.95) but no significant.	In this prospective cohort of subfertile couples, maternal \sum DEHP metabolite concentrations during pregnancy were associated with an increased risk of preterm birth, particularly during late gestation	Low + + / + + + +
Wu et al. (2022)/China	To elucidate the relationships between maternal exposure to EDCs and preterm birth	Meta-analysis	Not described	59 studies	Maternal exposure to phthalates (OR = 1.31; 95 % CI, 1.21–1.42) was related to an increased risk for PTB.	Maternal exposure to MEP, MECPP, MBzP, DEHP was associated with PTB	High + + + + / + + + +
Santos et al. (2021)/Netherlands	To assess the associations of maternal phthalate metabolites urine concentrations with fetal growth measures and birth outcomes and identify potential windows of vulnerability to exposure	Prospective cohort study (Generation R Study)	1379 pregnant women	Maternal phthalate metabolites urine concentrations at T1-T3	LMWP, HMWP and DEHP metabolites were associated with increased risk of PTB and small size for gestational age at birth ($p < 0.05$) Phthalic acid: OR = 0.90 (95 % CI: 0.58–1.42) LMWP: OR = 1.16 (95 % CI: 0.72, 1.86) HMWP: OR = 1.25 (95 % CI: 0.89, 1.76) DEHP: OR = 1.30 (95 % CI: 0.94, 1.81) DNOP: OR = 1.13 (95 % CI: 0.78, 1.65)	Higher maternal phthalate metabolites urine concentrations seem to be related with fetal growth restriction and PTB.	Very low + / + + + +
Hu et al. (2020)/USA-Canada	To examine the relation between prenatal urinary phthalate metabolite concentrations and PTB	Cohort study (MIREC)	1857 women	Urinary concentrations MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MCPP, MBzP, MEP, MnBP	No association between phthalate metabolite concentrations and PTB Male infants exposed to MCPP showed higher PTB risk compared with female infants	Phthalate exposure during early pregnancy is not clearly associated with the risk of PTB among this Canadian population	Very low + / + + + +
Zhang et al. (2020)/USA	To examine the association of paternal and maternal preconception urinary concentrations of biomarkers of phthalates and phthalate substitutes with singleton preterm birth	Cohort of subfertile couples	419 mothers and 229 fathers and their 420 live-born singleton offspring	Urinary concentrations of metabolites of phthalates before conception.	Preconception exposure to \sum DEHP and PTB association was observed (RR = 1.69; 95 % CI: 1.17–2.44; $p = 0.006$)	Maternal preconception exposure to \sum DEHP metabolites was associated with an increased risk of PTB.	Low + + / + + + +

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Table 5 (continued)

Author(s) (year)/country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
Broe et al. (2019)/Denmark	To determine whether phthalate exposure from pharmaceutical drugs have effects on PTB	Nested case-control study	1965 PTBs matched to 19,537, controls	Phthalate metabolites	Orthophthalate exposure at T3 was positively associated with PTB (OR = 1.36, 95 % CI: 1.06–1.76). The association was mainly due to DEP. Exposure to phthalate polymers at T3 was associated with a risk of PTB (OR = 2.08, CI: 1.16–3.71)	Exposure to some phthalate-containing pharmaceutical drugs at T3 is associated with PTB	Moderate +++ /++++
Bloom et al. (2019)/USA	To assess the maternal risks of gestational exposure by race and infant sex.	Cohort study	Pregnant African American (n = 152) and white (n = 158) women	MBP, MiBP, MBzP, MEHP, MEOHP, MEHHP, MEP, MMP, ΣDEHP and ΣDBP in urine	African Americans were at greater PTB risk than whites for greater MiBP [OR = 2.03 (95 % CI: 0.85–4.83) vs. OR = 0.55 (95 % CI: 0.16–1.83), respectively] (p = 0.08) and MEPP [OR = 1.46 (95 % CI: 0.97–2.19) vs. OR = 0.62 (95 % CI: 0.34–1.23) (p = 0.02) although lower risk for greater MEHPP [OR = 0.98 (95 % CI: 0.34–2.80) vs. OR = 3.40 (95 % CI: 1.24–9.31) (p = 0.09)	Gestational phthalate exposure is associated with adverse maternal birth outcomes, and that the effects vary by maternal race and infant sex	Very low + /++++
X.K. Wang et al. (2016)/USA	To study the mechanism behind phthalates exposure and preterm birth	Observational study	Term human placentas from healthy women following Caesarean section without labor	MEHP, CRH and COX-2, RelB/p52 heterodimers, NIK	MEHP increased CRH and COX-2 mRNA and protein abundance in a dose-dependent manner in primary cultures of cytotrophoblast	A potential mechanism mediated by RelB/p52 by which phthalates could prematurely induce pro-labor gene activity and lead to PTB.	Low + /++++
Ferguson et al. (2015b)/USA	To study associations between phthalate metabolites and biomarkers of oxidative stress measured in urine samples from multiple time points during pregnancy.	Nested case-control study	130 cases, 352 controls	9 phthalate metabolites, 8-OHdG and 8-isoprostane	All phthalate metabolites were associated with higher 8-OHdG concentrations: MBzP (20.7 %; 95 % CI: 15.6–26.1 %), MBP (18.1 %; 95 % CI: 13.5–22.9 %), and MiBP (30.3 %; 95 % CI: 24.4–36.5 %). All metabolites were associated with significantly higher 8-isoprostane concentrations: MBzP (42.7 %; 95 % CI: 31.8–54.4 %), MBP (42.0 %; 95 % CI: 32.0–52.7 %), and MiBP (56.4 %; 95 % CI: 43.9–69.9 %).	Urinary phthalate metabolites were associated with increased oxidative stress biomarkers in this study population of pregnant women	Moderate +++ /++++
Ferguson et al. (2014c)/USA-Puerto Rico	To investigate the associations between urinary phthalate metabolites and biomarkers of inflammation.	Observational study (PROTECT program)	139 women	11 phthalate metabolites: High molecular weight: MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, MBzP, MCP, MCOP, and MCNP Low molecular weight: MBP, MiBP, and MEP Biomarkers of inflammation: C-reactive protein, IL-1β, IL-6, IL-10, and TNF-α and oxidative stress: OHdG and 8-isoprostane	Most HMW phthalate metabolites associated with IL-6 (only significant for MCNP) and IL-10 (only significant for MECPP) No associations detected between metabolites of LMW phthalates and inflammation biomarkers MBP and MiBP: strong association with OHdG All phthalates tested showed significant association with isoprostane (except MEP)	There is an relationship between maternal phthalate exposure during pregnancy and systemic oxidative stress and inflammation	Low ++ /++++
Cathey et al. (2022b)/USA	To assess mediating effects of hormone concentrations on associations between phthalate mixtures and PTB	Cohort study	1011 women	Urinary phthalates and serum hormones	Free thyroxine (FT4) mediated 9.6 % of the association between HMW ERS at 18 weeks and reduced gestational age at delivery (95 % CI: 1.07–29.9). Progesterone at 26 weeks mediated 21.1 % and 16.2 % of the association between HMW ERS at 18 and 22	Hormone disruption could be on the causal pathway between phthalate exposure and early delivery.	Low ++ /++++

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Table 5 (continued)

Author(s) (year)/country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
Welch et al. (2023)/USA	To investigate race and ethnicity in the relationship between biomarkers of phthalate exposure and preterm birth	Cohort study	6045 women	Nine urinary phthalate metabolite concentrations by race and ethnicity	weeks, and spontaneous PTB, respectively. Metabolite concentrations were consistently higher among Black and Hispanic/Latina participants by 23 %–148 % and 4 %–94 %, respectively.	Phthalate metabolite concentrations differed substantially by race and ethnicity	Low +++/+++++
Liu et al. (2024)/China	To comprehensively explore the risk of maternal EDCs related to adverse pregnancy outcomes	Meta-analysis	101 studies	EDCs exposure (PFAS, phthalates, pheno/paraben, and organochlorine observed in serum, plasma, whole blood, urine, and cord blood)	Maternal phthalates exposure, such as MBP, MEHP, DEHP is associated with PTB (OR: 1.16, 95 % CI: 1.11–1.21)	Maternal PFAS, phthalates and BPA exposure may increase adverse pregnancy outcomes risk (SGA, miscarriage, LBW and PTB)	High ++++/+++++

Abbreviations. aOR: adjusted Odds Ratio, aRR: Adjusted Risk Ratio, BBP: butyl benzyl phthalate, BPA: bisphenol A, CI: confidence interval, CRH: corticotropin-releasing hormone, DBP: dibutyl phthalate, DEH: diethylhexyl phthalate, DEP: diethyl phthalate, DiBP: diisobutyl phthalate, DHEP: di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, DIBP: diisobutyl phthalate, DINP: diisononyl phthalate, EDCs: Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals, ERS: environmental risk score, FT4: Free thyroxine, GA: Gestational age, HMW: high molecular weight, HMWP: high molecular weight phthalate, HR: hazard ratio, IC: confidence interval, IQR: Interquartile range, LBW: low birth weight, LMWP: low molecular weight phthalate, LPTB: LatePreterm Birth, MBzP: mono-benzyl phthalate, MCP: mono(3-carboxypropyl) phthalate, MECPP: mono(2-ethyl-5-carboxyphenyl) phthalate, MEHHP: mono(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate, MEOHP: mono(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate, MEP: mono-ethyl phthalate, MHINP: mono-hydroxy-isononyl phthalate, MiBP: mono-isobutyl phthalate, MnBP: mono-n-butyl phthalate, MOiNP: mono-oxo-isononyl phthalate, MOP: mono-n-octyl phthalate, NIK: NF-kB inducing kinase, OH-MnBP: 3OH-mono-n-butyl phthalate, OHdG: 8-hydroxydeoxyguanosine, OR: Odds Ratio, PFAS: polyfluoroalkyl substances; PTB: Preterm birth, SGA: small for gestational age; SLE: Stressful life event, sPTB: spontaneous preterm birth, T1: first trimester of pregnancy; T2: second trimester of pregnancy; T3: third trimester of pregnancy; v: visit, Σ DEHP: Summed di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate. Quality of evidence grades: high (+++++), moderate (+++), low (++) , very low (+).

mediated by the non-oxidative energy metabolism of the maternal body during pregnancy was between 7 and 15 % (Thomson et al., 2023).

The prenatal presence of MEHHP was also associated with an increase in attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) symptoms (OR = 2.98) in children aged 2.5 and 11 years, in both sexes (Ku et al., 2020). Kim et al. also showed that a 2.7 fold increase in MEHHP during pregnancy was associated with an 8.5 % increase in the social communication questionnaire (SCQ) score, a screening instrument for ASD. The authors also observed a positive association between MEHHP and autistic traits at 4 years of age. The association was stronger in boys (Kim et al., 2021).

The prenatal presence of mixed phthalate metabolites has also been positively associated with behavioral disorders, such as ADHD. Children born to mothers in the highest quintile of Σ DEHP in the second trimester were almost three times more likely to be diagnosed with ADHD than those born to mothers in the lowest quintile [OR = 2.99 (95 % CI: 1.47, 5.49)] (Engel et al., 2018). Of note is the study by Ku et al. in which they assessed temperament at 2, 5 and 11 years of age and also concluded that prenatal exposure (in this case in the third trimester) to Σ DEHP produces an increased in OR of up to 3.3 for ADHD symptomatic features in children at 11 years of age (also in both sexes). Although this association tends to weaken with age (Ku et al., 2020).

DBP, mainly found in paints and personal care products, increased the OR by 25–40 % for language delay in boys aged 3 years by 25–40 % for every doubling of prenatal exposure to DBP in the first trimester (Bornehag et al., 2018). This study compared cohorts from two different countries and found the same results. The study of its metabolites, such as MBP, also showed significant results in boys aged 2–4 years, in terms of autistic behavior and social impairment, as well as increased reaction times (Rolland et al., 2023; Alampi et al., 2021; Oulhote et al., 2020) and a negative association with executive function (Choi et al., 2021). However, these studies collected single urine samples to determine phthalate exposure during pregnancy, without monitoring its variation over time. In addition, most of the studies used the social responsiveness scale (SRS-2 test), which is not designed to diagnose ASD.

BBzP, used in the production of polyvinyl chloride (PVC)-based flooring material, deodorants, food packaging and adhesives, was also correlated with language delay in males (OR: 1.26 (95 % CI: 1.07–1.49)), as was DBP (Bornehag et al., 2018). Its metabolite, mono-benzyl phthalate, used to monitor the exposure to BBzP, was one of the most common metabolites in the studies reviewed, with a significant effect in 8 studies (Choi et al., 2021; Alampi et al., 2021; Torres-Olascoaga et al., 2020; Ku et al., 2020; Park et al., 2023; Patti et al., 2021). While Patti et al. found a positive association of MBzP with ASD features in children with ASD risk, without distinguishing between sexes (Patti et al., 2021), Shin et al. found a positive association with non-typical development risk but not with ASD in boys with ASD risk (Shin et al., 2018). Consistent with Patti et al., the work of Alampi et al. also found an association between higher exposure to MBzP and higher SRS scores. In this case, the authors determined that gender was able to modify this association, with significant results only in boys. These discrepancies between autistic behaviors and MBzP exposure may be due to the use of different tests (SRS-2, ADOS-2 and MSEL), the low population size in the work of Shin et al., and the use of populations at high and low risk of ASD between studies. The presence of BBzP in the second and third trimesters was also associated with a 3 % reduction in attentional control in eye-tracking tasks (Rolland et al., 2023), as well as poorer working memory, inhibition and emotional control (Choi et al., 2021) and a lower General Cognitive Index, an equivalent to intellectual coefficient and motor scale (Torres-Olascoaga et al., 2020). Similarly, prenatal exposure to MBzP in the third trimester also increased the ORs to 9.12 for ADHD symptomatic features at two years of age (Ku et al., 2020).

Other metabolites such as MEP, from the parental phthalate DEP, present in personal care products, has been associated with autistic behaviors in boys at low risk of autism aged 3–6 years (Alampi et al.,

2021; Haggerty et al., 2021), increasing the SRS-2 t-score by 0.9 points for each doubling of MEP concentration (Haggerty et al., 2021). Bornehag et al. also observed a 15 % increased OR for language delay for each doubling of prenatal exposure to MEP in both boys and girls, although this percentage was lower than for DBP and BBzP (Bornehag et al., 2018). The main effects of phthalate metabolites on infant neurodevelopment are shown in Fig. 4.

4. Discussion

This systematic review has shown how exposure to phthalates during pregnancy negatively affects both maternal health and fetal neurodevelopment. The findings presented throughout the study regarding the effect of prenatal phthalate exposure on maternal GDM, weight gain, PIH, FGR, PTB and their effects on fetal neurodevelopment alert us to the daily relationship between these compounds and their short and long term consequences in such a vulnerable population.

Although some studies in relation to GDM are controversial, recent evidence shows that environmental exposure to these endocrine disrupting chemicals can affect glucose metabolism, leading to glucose disorders and obesity during critical periods of pregnancy. The main mechanism is the activation of PPARs, which modulate cellular lipid and glucose metabolism, and decrease insulin receptor expression (Rajesh and Balasubramanian, 2014). Studies in rodents have shown that exposure to phthalates may impair glucose metabolism through various mechanisms. Experimental studies have reported that several phthalates can activate peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPAR). PPAR α / β play important roles in hepatic and muscle fatty acid catabolism, and PPAR γ in adipogenesis and lipid storage. Binding of these receptors to some endocrine disruptors could increase the fat storage in mature adipocytes leading to insulin resistance. In animal studies, DEHP has hepatotoxic properties through a mechanism involving PPAR α , so chronic exposure may cause abnormal glucose metabolite flux in liver and skeletal muscle with reduction of hepatic glycolysis and altered lactate production in skeletal muscle. MEHP decreased the proliferation of Sertoli cells, which have anti-androgenic properties. Thus, phthalate exposure may affect fertility, energy balance, and glucose homeostasis (Desvergne et al., 2009; Martinelli et al., 2006; Karabulut and Barlas, 2021). DEP administration in rodents caused a decline in the protein concentration of the key glucose transporters GLUT2 and GLUT4, which reduces cellular glucose uptake (Mondal and Mukherjee, 2020). Therefore, phthalates may interfere with normal glucose metabolism by impairing insulin signaling, inducing oxidative stress and causing β -cell dysfunction, leading to hyperglycemia in humans (Kim et al., 2013; Ding et al., 2019). In addition, maternal exposure to environmental pollutants such as phthalates may cause an epigenetic transgenerational effects that alter glucose pathways in the offspring (Venturelli et al., 2019). It has also been described that the overexpression of miRNA associated with the development of GDM in early pregnancy is associated with exposure to phthalates, supporting the hypothesis that phthalates alter glucose metabolism (Martínez-Ibarra et al., 2019). Moreover, it seems likely that the first trimester is the period most vulnerable to these effects on maternal GDM and gestational weight gain. The early stages of embryonic development are characterized by major epigenetic changes events, including removal and reprogramming of parental DNA methylation. Phthalates impair placental function by modifying the expression of critical placental genes through epigenetic modifications (Zuccarello et al., 2022; Grindler et al., 2018). The obesogenic and insulin resistance effects of phthalates through their action on PPAR pathways increase the risk of metabolic complications when exposure occurs during the first trimester (Gao et al., 2021). Regarding the effects of phthalates on GDM and GWG, it is difficult to find an association depending on the type of metabolite (LMWP and HMWP). The studies that didn't find an association between phthalate metabolites and glucose levels included HMWP metabolites (Shapiro et al., 2015; Robledo et al., 2015). However, the studies that included both types of

metabolites found an exposure to pollutants and impaired glucose metabolism (Liang et al., 2022; W. Chen et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023; Fisher et al., 2018; Shaffer et al., 2019; James-Tod et al., 2016; James-Todd et al., 2022; Gao et al., 2021). Nevertheless, in experimental studies, MEHP and DEHP (HMW phthalates) are the most commonly described metabolites that interact with the PPAR pathway and alter lipid and glucose metabolism (Desvergne et al., 2009; Martinelli et al., 2006; Karabulut and Barlas, 2021; Ding et al., 2019).

For PIH and FGR, the evidence reviewed suggests a positive association for both (Zhao et al., 2015, 2014, 2016; Soomro et al., 2021, 2023; Bedell et al., 2021; Cantonwine et al., 2016; Werner et al., 2015; Guo et al., 2022; Santos et al., 2021; Miura et al., 2021; Ferguson et al., 2016; Bloom et al., 2019; Zang et al., 2023; Lenters et al., 2016; Huang et al., 2014; Stevens et al., 2023a; Li et al., 2021; Shirangi et al., 2020), although, as for GDM, the data should be interpreted with caution because the included studies had different methodological approaches. Specifically, according to the evaluation of the exposure time and the matrix analyzed. Studies conducted in early pregnancy, the most vulnerable stage for endocrine disruptors, were also more reliable for the effects of phthalates in the PIH and FGR (Bedell et al., 2021; Cantonwine et al., 2016; Philips et al., 2019; LaRocca et al., 2014; Shirangi et al., 2020), but prevent an evaluation of the cumulative effects of phthalates on fetal development. The first trimester of pregnancy is an important period during which a number of crucial developmental events occur, such as fetal organogenesis and placental development. Any adverse effect at this stage may result in an increased risk of PIH and FGR due to premature placental abnormalities, which can be evaluated by angiogenic factors, such as the sFlt-1/PlGF ratio (Philips et al., 2019). For this reason, early pregnancy is considered an important window in which exposure to phthalates may be associated with an increased risk of developing PIH or FGR later in pregnancy. With regard to FGR, the main outcomes analyzed in the studies included in this review were EFW, FGR or LBW. These variables provide a more complete and comprehensive view of fetal health and development, but it would be interesting to expand the search in future reviews to include other variables such as fetal biometrics (biparietal diameter, head circumference, abdominal circumference, femur length) (Stevens et al., 2023b) or differences in anogenital distance (Barrett et al., 2016). The consequences of phthalate exposure on pregnancy health and fetal development are explained by different mechanisms of action. The PIH and FGR induced by prenatal phthalate exposure share similar pathophysiological mechanisms, specifically endocrine disruption through the rennin-angiotensin-aldosterone or cortisol secretion (Warembourg et al., 2019; Miura et al., 2021; Bloom et al., 2019), thyroid and hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis disruption (Miura et al., 2021; Bloom et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2018; Zhong et al., 2021), changes in DNA methylation (Zhao et al., 2015, 2016; Soomro et al., 2023; LaRocca et al., 2014; Miura et al., 2021), proinflammatory effects (Stevens et al., 2022), placental abnormalities (Santos et al., 2021; Bloom et al., 2019), alterations in circulating placental angiogenic biomarkers (Ferguson et al., 2015a), estrogenic and antiandrogenic effects (Bloom et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2018; Zhong et al., 2021) and induction of oxidative stress (Zhao et al., 2015, 2016; Sathyanarayana et al., 2016; Cowell et al., 2023). Some of these mechanisms have been studied in detail in several experimental and observational studies. Some authors have shown the disruptive effect of phthalates on placental development. Ferguson et al. evaluated in an observational study the association of DEHP with decreased PlGF levels and increased sFlt-1/PlGF ratio (Ferguson et al., 2015a), predictive angiogenic biomarkers of preeclampsia. Moreover, Bhurke et al. (Bhurke et al., 2023) showed in a mouse model prenatally exposed to DiNP the impairment of decidual angiogenesis and placental development with the consequent negative impact on fetal growth. Another important mechanism involved in FGR is the endocrine disrupting effect of phthalates, as described by Yu et al. (Yu et al., 2018) in a mouse model prenatally exposed to DEHP, in which placental mRNA levels of Thr α 1 and Thr β 1 were reduced, as well as several THR downstream genes

Table 6
Summary of studies based on the effect of maternal prenatal phthalates on infant neurodevelopment.

Author(s) (year)/country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
Day et al. (2021)/USA	To investigate associations between maternal prenatal phthalates and neurobehavioral outcomes in children at 4–5 years of age.	Prospective observational study. Multicentric	501 children (4–5 years) from mothers exposed to phthalates	Neurobehavioral assessments in children: Questionnaires: BASC-2 SRS-2 9 phthalate metabolites in prenatal urine samples at T1 and T3	Early pregnancy: Associations with autistic traits in both sexes Late pregnancy: Association with hyperactivity and aggression in males DEHP metabolites highly associated with neurobehavioral outcomes in boys MEP, MBP, and MiBP highly associated with neurobehavioral outcomes in girls Phthalate metabolites detected in >80 % of samples M24: MCPP associated with lower adaptive, cognitive, communication, motor and personal-social scores M6: Boys: Σ DEHTP significantly associated with adaptive and cognitive domains Girls: MBZP significantly associated with communication domain scores MEP significantly associated with communication domain scores M12: Boys: MEP and MCOP associated with lower adaptive domain Boys: MCOP associated with lower cognitive and motor scores M24: Boys: Σ DEHTP associated with adaptive domain	Exposure to phthalates during pregnancy was associated with increased autistic traits and adverse behavioral outcomes in childhood	Low ++/++++
Park et al. (2023)/Puerto Rico	Examine associations between phthalate metabolite concentrations and adaptive, personal-social, communication, motor and cognitive domains	Prospective observational study. Multicentric	274 children from PROTECT study	Neurobehavioral assessments in children at M6, M12 and M24 Questionnaires: BDI-2 Phthalate metabolites in prenatal urine samples in T2 (18,22 and 26 weeks of gestation)	M24: MCPP associated with lower adaptive, cognitive, communication, motor and personal-social scores M6: Boys: Σ DEHTP significantly associated with adaptive and cognitive domains Girls: MBZP significantly associated with communication domain scores MEP significantly associated with communication domain scores M12: Boys: MEP and MCOP associated with lower adaptive domain Boys: MCOP associated with lower cognitive and motor scores M24: Boys: Σ DEHTP associated with adaptive domain	Maternal exposure to phthalates may have adverse effects on on child neurodevelopment during infancy, with differences according to sex and child age	Low ++/++++
Thomson et al. (2023)/Australia	To determine the relationship between the presence of phthalates in utero with maternal and infant metabolic energy profiles and later symptoms of ASD in early childhood.	Prospective observational study. Unicentric	1074 mother–infant pairs	Phthalate metabolites in prenatal urine samples at 36 weeks of gestation (T3) Metabolomic analysis in maternal serum, umbilical cord serum, and children’s plasma samples Questionnaire measures of ASD symptoms at 2 and 4 years: CBCL-ASP and SDQ-peer.	98 %-100 % of women had detectable levels of DEHP, DEP, DiBP and DnBP metabolites Higher DEHP exposure associated with higher pyruvate, lactate and alanine levels CBCL-ASP at M24: mean change of 0.17 points (95 % CI 0.03, 0.31) for a 1 SD increase in pyruvate mean change of 0.15 points (95 % CI 0.01, 0.29) for a 1 SD increase in citrate mean change of 0.19 points (95 % CI 0.04, 0.33) for a 1 SD increase in alanine	Higher levels of prenatal DEHP exposure upregulates maternal non-oxidative energy metabolism and increase the likelihood of offspring ASD symptoms.	Low ++/++++

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Table 6 (continued)

Author(s) (year)/ country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
					SDQ-peer at M48: mean change of 0.18 points (95 % CI 0.07, 0.28) for a 1 SD increase in pyruvate mean change of 0.19 points (95 % CI 0.08, 0.29) for a 1 SD increase in citrate mean change of 0.14 points (95 % CI 0.04, 0.24) for a 1 SD increase in lactate No metabolic results were found in cord blood or at one year of age related with both prenatal phthalate exposure and ASD symptoms.		
Rolland et al. (2023)/ France	To analyze the association between prenatal exposure to phthalates and neurodevelopment at two years of age	Prospective observational study	479 mothers 151 infants	15 biomarkers of phthalate exposure in prenatal urine samples at T2, T3 and urine at M12 Eye-tracking tasks performed at M24: 1) Mean fixation durations: a marker of attentional control 2) Novelty preference: a measure of recognition/visual memory 3) Percent time spent looking at the eyes 4) Mean reaction time: a marker of processing speed	MBzP: Decreased the fixation duration by 2.5 % (95 % CI: -5.4; 0.44) and 3.0 % (95 % CI: -5.5; -0.43) for each doubling of its concentration at T2 and T3, respectively. Infant levels not associated with any scores MnBP: Associated in T2 with longer reaction times in boys ($\beta = 21$ ms (95 % CI: 2.1; 41)) but not in girls ($\beta = -8.6$ ms (95 % CI: -25; 7.5)). MiBP and MEP: Negatively associated with reaction time MiBP: negative association between girls exposure and the time spent looking at the eyes	Exposure to LMW phthalates at 12 months and MBzP during pregnancy are associated with autism traits at 24 months.	Very low +/++++
Parenti et al. (2022)/ USA	Investigate the associations between: 1) Maternal phthalate exposure and maternal serum metabolites in T3 and placental metabolites 2) Serum and placental metabolomes and neurodevelopmental outcomes	Prospective observational study	160 mother-child pairs with high familial ASD risk	14 phthalate metabolites in urine samples at T2 and T3 Serum at T3 and placental metabolomes Child Neurodevelopmental Assessment at M36: ADOS and MSEL	No significant associations between phthalate metabolites and serum metabolites No significant associations between serum metabolites and neurodevelopmental outcomes Negative direct effect of the phthalate mixture on placental glucitol, carnitine, O-acetylcarnitine, N-acetylneuraminic acid, and 2-hydroxybutyrate	Neurodevelopmental outcome associated with the placental metabolome in male children. Maternal serum metabolome not related to either phthalate exposure or neurodevelopmental outcome.	Very low +/++++
Patti et al. (2021)/ USA	Investigate the associations between gestational phthalate exposure and child ASD-related behaviors	Prospective observational study. Multicentric	140 mothers with a child with ASD 276 mothers from a general population cohort	9 phthalate metabolites in urine samples at T1-T3 ASD-related behaviors at age 3-8 years using the SRS scale	General population cohort: positive associations of MBP, MBzP, MiBP, MCPP, and Σ DEHP concentrations with parent-reported ASD-related behaviors at higher percentiles (≥ 75 %) of child SRS T-scores Risk ASD cohort: positive association of MBzP with SRS T-score from 50th to 95th percentiles of the SRS T-scores	Urinary concentrations of phthalate metabolites during pregnancy are associated with ASD traits in children with higher SRS scores	Very low +/++++

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Table 6 (continued)

Author(s) (year)/ country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
Choi et al. (2021)/ Norway	Evaluate the relationship between prenatal phthalate exposure and the preschool executive function	Retrospective cohort study	262 children with ADHD symptoms (3.5-years) 78 neurotypical children (aged 3.5-years)	12 phthalate metabolites in urine samples at weeks' gestation (T2) Evaluation of the EF: BRIEF-P, CDT, SB5	100 % of urine samples had detectable concentrations of all phthalate metabolites. MBzP associated with poorer working memory, inhibition, emotional control in both sex MiBP and MnBP during pregnancy associated with poorer EF (working memory, worse emotional control and inhibition) among boys Not notable associations with DEHP or DiNP and EF. MCPP and sum of the DEHPs:	MBzP, MiBP, and MnBP during pregnancy are associated with poorer EF in offspring.	Very low +/++++
Alampi et al. (2021)/ Canada	To analyze the relationships of exposure to toxicants during T1 with ASD-associated behaviors in preschool children.	Retrospective cohort study. Multicentric	600 mother-child pairs (aged 3-4 years)	10 phthalate metabolites in urine at T1 Autistic behaviors: SRS-2	A 2-fold increase in gestational urinary concentrations at the upper tail of the SRS distribution is associated with increased SRS scores ($\beta = 0.9 = 0.79$, 95 % adjusted posterior credible interval: 0.24, 1.34) and ($\beta = 0.9 = 0.70$, 95 % posterior credible interval: 0.14, 1.26), respectively MBP, MEP and MBzP: stronger association in boys	Children with the most autistic-like behaviors are particularly vulnerable to phthalates	Low ++/++++
Kim et al. (2021)/ South Korea	Identify which periods are most susceptible to the effect of phthalates on autistic traits	Longitudinal prospective study	547 mother-child pairs	5 phthalate metabolites in urine and blood at T2 Childhood phthalate metabolite levels in urine at age of 4, 6, and 8 years Autistic behaviors: SCQ at 4 years	A 2.7-fold increase of MEHHP and MEOHP in pregnancy and childhood showed: Pregnancy: an increase of 8.5 % (95 % CI: 1.9 %, 15.5 %) and 7.4 % (95 % CI: 0.3 %, 15.0 %) in SCQ scores at 4 years of age Childhood: i) 4 years of age: increase of SCQ scores at 8 years (9.9 % change [95 % CI: 1.8 %, 18.6 %]; 12.9 % change [95 % CI: 3.6 %, 23.1 %], respectively) ii) 8 years of age: increase of SCQ scores at age 8 9.6 % change [95 % CI: 1.3 %, 18.6 %]; 12.3 % change [95 % CI: 3.8 %, 21.5 %]. MnBP also related: 8.9 % change [95 % CI: 1.2 %, 17.1 %] MEHHP exposure at pregnancy and at the age of 4 years significantly associated with SCQ in boys at 4, 6 and 8 years of age	Exposure to phthalates during pregnancy is associated with autistic traits in young children Exposure during the early years produces autistic traits in school-aged children, especially in boys	Low ++/++++
Haggerty et al. (2021)/ USA	To assess the relationship between prenatal exposure to phthalates and ASD traits, gender, and behavioral problems	Prospective cohort study	77 mother-child pairs (aged 3-6 years)	7 phthalate metabolites in prenatal urine and blood at T1 and T2 Autistic behaviors: SRS-2	Girls: prenatal urinary phthalate metabolites were not significantly associated with SRS-2 score Boys: 0.9 point increase of SRS-2 t-score	MEP associated with SRS-2 sex- and age-adjusted t-scores among boys	Very low +/++++

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Table 6 (continued)

Author(s) (year)/ country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
Ku et al. (2020)/ Taiwan	Identify the association between prenatal phthalates exposure and postnatal temperament	Prospective cohort study	208 mother–child pairs	General behavior problems: CBCL 7 phthalate metabolites in prenatal (T3) and childhood urine Temperament evaluations by caretakers at 2, 5 and 11 years of age: CTTS, BSQ-C (for ages 5+) and Middle Childhood Temperament Questionnaire–Chinese version (for age 11)	(95 % CI: 0.1, 1.7) for each doubling of MEP concentration Increased ORs for ADHD symptomatic features: MEHHP: OR = 2.98 (95 % CI: 1.05–8.48) Sum of the DEHP metabolites: OR = 3.28 (1.15–9.35) MBzP: OR = 9.12 (95 % CI: 1.07–78.06) No differences between sexes Total SRS score:	An increased phthalate exposure in pregnant women and their children is associated with maladaptive temperamental outcomes	Low ++/++++
Oulhote et al. (2020)/ Canada	Identify the association between prenatal phthalates exposure (T1) and autistic traits	Prospective cohort study. Multicentric	610 children (aged 3–4 years)	11 phthalate metabolites in prenatal (T1) urine Autistic behaviors and social impairment: SRS-2	MBP: a two-fold increase in urine associated with \uparrow 0.6 points (95 % CI: 0.1, 1.0) MCPP: a two-fold increase in urine associated with \uparrow 0.5 points (95 % CI: 0.1, 0.8) MBP in boys: a two-fold increase in urine associated with \uparrow 1.0, 1.1, 0.9 and 0.9 in Total, Social Cognition, Social Communication, and Restricted Interests and Repetitive Behavior scores No associations observed for MBzP, MEP, and DEHP.	Higher gestational concentrations of some phthalate metabolites are associated with higher scores of autistic traits in boys, but not in girls	Low ++/++++
Ponsonby et al. (2020)/ Australia	Investigate the interplay between maternal prenatal phthalate levels, genetic vulnerability to oxidative stress, and neurodevelopment	Prospective cohort study. Multicentric	1074 mother–infant pairs (aged 3–4 years)	10 phthalate metabolites in prenatal (T3) urine Genome-wide genotyping Cognitive Development scale: BAYLEY-III SDQ ASD assessments by a pediatrician	Σ phthalates (per SD unit increase): ASD \rightarrow AOR: 1.65 (95 % CI 1.00, 2.72) ASD traits \rightarrow AOR: 1.65 (95 % CI 1.23, 2.23) A doubling of Σ phthalates and DEHP + oxidative stress-related genetic score: ASD traits \rightarrow OR: 2.23 and 2.4, respectively	Prenatal phthalate levels and a higher infant oxidative stress gene score are associated with adverse neurodevelopment	Low ++/++++
Torres-Olascoaga et al. (2020)/ Mexico	Identify windows of susceptibility to the effects of gestational exposure to HMWPs on neurodevelopment at 48 months	Prospective cohort study. Multicentric	214 mother–infant pairs	6 phthalate metabolites in prenatal (T1–T3) urine Cognitive abilities (MSCA test): children’s motor, cognitive and memory abilities	T1: significant negative association between HMWP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP and DEHP and motor scale Significant negative association for boys between MBzP and the General Cognitive Index T2: significant negative association between HMWP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, MBzP, and DEHP and motor scale T3: no associations	T1 is the most sensitive window of exposure to HMWP for neurodevelopment, particularly in boys.	Low ++/++++
Engel et al. (2018)/ Norway	To relate prenatal biomarkers of phthalate exposure to clinical ADHD in offspring	Prospective, nested case–control study	297 clinically diagnosed cases of ADHD and 553 control mother–child pairs	12 phthalate metabolites in prenatal (T2) urine TSH, Triiodothyronine and thyroxine in maternal blood at T2	Strong association between Σ DEHP and ADHD in both sexes No evidence of mediation of the Σ DEHP–ADHD relationship by TSH, Triiodothyronine or thyroxine	Maternal prenatal exposure to Σ DEHP is associated with increased risk of ADHD in offspring.	Low ++/++++

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Table 6 (continued)

Author(s) (year)/ country	Objectives	Study design	Population	Variables studied	Key results	Conclusion	Quality of evidence
Jones et al. (2018)/ Singapore	To investigate associations between the maternal hair metabolome and variation in child neurocognitive development	Prospective cohort study. Multicentric	373 infant-mother pairs	Untargeted metabolome in maternal hair samples at T3 Cognitive Development scale: BAYLEY-III (at 2 years of age)	High levels of phthalic acid associated with lower language scores on the BAYLEY-III ($p = 0.022$) No associations between identified metabolites and receptive language, cognitive or motor scores First month of pregnancy:	Association between high levels of phthalates and lower language ability	Low ++/++++
Shin et al. (2018)/ USA	To determine the association between prenatal exposure to phthalates and an increased risk of ASD.	Prospective observational study	201 mother-child pairs with a high-risk of ASD	14 phthalate metabolites in urine samples at T2-T3 Child Neurodevelopmental Assessment at M36: ADOS and MSEL	Non-TD risk positively associated with: MCP: RRR = 5.09 (95 % CI: 2.05, 12.6) MCOP: RRR = 1.86 (95 % CI: 1.01, 3.39) MCNP: RRR = 3.67 (95 % CI: 1.80, 7.48) MEP: RRR = 1.38 (95 % CI: 1.01, 1.90) Boys: Positive association with Non-TD risk: MEP, MBzP, MCP, MCNP, and Σ DEHP Null association with ASD Girls: null association with ASD or Non-TD	Phthalate exposures in T2-T3 is not associated with ASD. Although these results cannot be generalizable to the general population	Low ++/++++
Bornehag et al. (2018)/ Sweden- USA	To examine the association between the metabolite phthalate level in urine samples at T1 and language development in early childhood	Prospective cohort study. Multicentric	Two pregnancy cohorts: 963 mother-child pairs from SELMA study (Sweden) 370 mother-child pairs from TIDES study (USA)	SELMA study cohort: 10 phthalate metabolites in prenatal urine samples at T1 Parental questionnaire for language development at 30 months of age TIDES study cohort: 11 phthalate metabolites in prenatal urine samples at T1 Parental questionnaire for language development at 37 months of age	DBP and BBzP: increased OR by 25–40 % for language delay MEP: increased OR by 15 % for language delay Dose-response association between MBzP and language delay (trend) DEHP: no association with language delay	Exposure to DBP and BBzP in T1 is associated with poorer language development in children aged 2.5 to 3 years	Low ++/++++
Minatoya et al. (2016)/ Japan	To evaluate the associations between prenatal DEHP exposure and mental and psychomotor development in infants	Prospective cohort study. Unicentric	328 mother-child pairs	DEHP levels in maternal blood samples at T2-T3 Mental and psychomotor development: BSID-II at 6 and 18 months of age	BSID 6 and 18 months: no significant results in Mental Development or Psychomotor Development index related to DEHP level	No association between prenatal DEHP exposure and infant mental and psychomotor development in infants	Low ++/++++

Abbreviations. ADHD: attention deficit hyperactivity disorder; ADOS: autism spectrum disorder diagnostic observation schedule; AOR: adjusted odds ratio; ASD: autism spectrum disorder; BASC-2: behavioral assessment system for children; BAYLEY-III: Bayley scales of infant and toddler development 3rd edition; BBzP: butyl benzyl phthalate; BDI-2: battelle developmental inventory-2nd edition; BRIEF-P: rating inventory of executive function-preschool; BSID-II: II Bayley scales of infant development; BSQ-C: behavior style questionnaire-Chinese version; CBCL-ASP: child behavior checklist-autism spectrum problems; CDT: cookie delay task; CTTS: Chinese toddler temperament scale; DBP: dibutyl phthalate; DEHP: diethylhexylphthalate; DEP: diethyl phthalate; DiBP: diisobutyl phthalate; DiNP: di-isononyl phthalate; DnBP: di-n-butyl phthalate; DQ: developmental quotient; EF: executive function; HMWP: high-molecular-weight phthalates; LMW: low molecular weight; M12: 12 month infancy; M24: 24 month infancy; M36: 36 month infancy; M48: 48 month infancy; M6: 6 month infancy; MBP: mono-butyl phthalate; MBzP: mono-benzyl phthalate; MCNP: mono-carboxyisononyl phthalate; MCOP: mono-carboxyisooctyl phthalate; MCP: mono(3-carboxypropyl) Phthalate; MEHHP: mono-(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate; MEOHP: mono-(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate; MEP: monoethyl phthalate; MiBP: mono-isobutyl phthalate; MnBP: mono-n-butyl phthalate; ms: milliseconds; MSCA: McCarthy scales of children's abilities; MSEL: Mullen scales of early learning; NEPSY: developmental neuropsychological assessment; Non-TD: non-typical development; ORs: odds ratios; RRR: relative risk ratio; SB5: Stanford-Binet intelligence test V; SCQ: social communication questionnaire; SDQ: strengths and difficulties questionnaire; SRS-2: social responsiveness scale; T1: first trimester; T2: second trimester; T3: third trimester; TSH: thyroid stimulating hormone; Σ DEHP: sum of di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate metabolites.

Quality of evidence grades: high (++++), moderate (+++), low (++) , very low (+).

Fig. 4. Main effects of parental phthalates and phthalate metabolites on neurodevelopment according to the studies reviewed. The distinction of effects by sex was made based on the results of the studies. Information in brackets indicates the trimester of pregnancy where maternal urine was obtained.

Abbreviations. ADHD: attention deficit hyperactivity disorder; BBzP: butyl benzyl phthalate; DBBP: dibutyl benzyl phthalate; DBP: dibutyl phthalate; MBP mono-butyl phthalate; MBzP: mono-benzyl phthalate; MCNP: mono-carboxyisononyl phthalate; MCOP: mono-carboxyisoctyl phthalate; MCP: mono(3-carboxypropyl) phthalate; MECPP: mono(2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) phthalate; MEHHP: mono-(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate; MEHP: mono-2-ethylhexyl phthalate; MEOHP: mono-(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate; MEP: monoethyl phthalate; MiBP: mono-isobutyl phthalate; MONP: mono oxononyl phthalate; T1: first trimester; T2: second trimester; T3: third trimester; Σ DEHP: sum of di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate metabolites; Σ DEHTP: sum of di-2-ethylhexyl terephthalate metabolites.

(Vegf, Pgf, Igf1 and Igf2) important for placental angiogenesis. Other authors studied the association between maternal exposure to phthalates and placental methylation disorders. Regarding epigenetics, Zhao et al. (Zhao et al., 2015) demonstrated a Σ DEHP-mediated reduction in placental LINE-1 methylation and an association with impaired fetal growth. However, LaRocca et al. (LaRocca et al., 2014) showed an association between maternal urinary phthalate metabolites and placental methylation dysregulation of the H19 and IGF2DMR0 imprinting genes, but, neither methylation nor expression of these imprinted regions had a significant effect on PIH or birth weight. When analyzing the differences between LMWP and HMWP, although some authors studied the effects according to this classification (Han et al., 2020; Philips et al., 2019; Santos et al., 2021), they did not find any differences in the risk of PIH or FGR. Nevertheless, because of the small number of studies that have analyzed the risk of PIH or FGR according to the molecular weight of the phthalates, it would be interesting in the future to consider studies with large populations to investigate whether the molecular weight might have some relationship with the occurrence of pregnancy complications.

Prenatal exposure to phthalates was also positively associated with PTB. Although the overall risk factor of phthalates for preterm birth remains weak according to published odds ratios (Liu et al., 2024), it is important to note that some meta-analyses reached statistically significant results (Wu et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2024). Depending on the time of exposure, urinary concentrations of several phthalate metabolites were similar in sPTB and controls in early pregnancy. However, as pregnancy progressed most metabolites (such as MECPP and Σ DEHP) showed the strongest association with PTB incidence (Ferguson et al., 2014c). This is understandable as both inflammation and oxidative stress are triggering mechanisms of PTB. A variety of different metabolites have been analyzed in maternal urine samples, but DEHP metabolites have been most strongly associated with PTB (Wu et al., 2022; Ferguson et al., 2014a, 2014b; Welch et al., 2022). Studies have also shown that phthalates increase inflammation, oxidative stress

and overexpression of pro-labor genes, promoting prematurity, and that phthalate metabolite concentrations vary significantly by race and ethnicity, with black and Hispanic populations having the highest phthalate levels and risk of PTB (Bloom et al., 2019; Harris et al., 2022; Welch et al., 2023). Ferguson et al. studied the effect of maternal phthalate exposure on biomarkers of oxidative stress and inflammation. DEHP metabolites were associated with increased levels of IL-6 and IL-10 (Ferguson et al., 2014c), as well as 8-hydroxydeoxyguanosine (OHdG) and 8-isoprostane (Ferguson et al., 2017, 2014c), and with an increased risk of PTB. Furthermore, in cytotrophoblast cultures, Wang et al. (X.K. Wang et al., 2016) showed a possible RelB/p52-mediated molecular mechanism by which MEHP could prematurely induce pro-labor gene activity and lead to PTB. As with other pregnancy complications, most authors do not evaluate the existence of differences in PTB according to the differentiation between LMWP and HMWP. Among the authors who have analyzed the effects on PTB according to the molecular weight of the phthalates, Santos et al. (Santos et al., 2021) report that both (LMWP and HMWP) are associated with an increased risk of PTB. On the other hand, Cathey et al. (Cathey et al., 2022a) found an association between HMWP and PTB.

This review also found an adverse association between prenatal phthalate exposure and fetal neurodevelopment, and that neuro-behavioral outcomes may be sex- and time-specific, particularly at the level of ASD-related behaviors. This may be because phthalates can reduce testosterone production and increase estrogen signaling (Sathyanarayana et al., 2017), affecting the development of sex-specific brain structures or impairing circuits specialized in social cognition (Xu et al., 2020; Lombardo et al., 2020). We have seen that boys are more likely to develop autistic traits than girls, particularly in relation to the prenatal presence of MBP, MEP, MBzP and MEHHP (Rolland et al., 2023; Alampi et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2021; Oulhote et al., 2020; Haggerty et al., 2021). Although it appears that there are no gender differences in other neurodevelopmental disorders such as ADHD or motor skills, we

cannot state this categorically, as more studies stratified by sex and with standardized criteria for measuring the outcomes are needed. Whether children at high risk of ASD (from mothers who have already had children with ASD) are more vulnerable to the neurotoxic effects of phthalates during the fetal period has not yet been elucidated. While some studies suggest a positive association between certain phthalates, such as MBzP and ASD traits (Patti et al., 2021), others find a non-typical developmental risk but null association with ASD (Shin et al., 2018). However, a strong association between MBP, MEP and MBzP and the high end of the SRS distribution seems likely, especially in boys (Alampí et al., 2021). It has also been shown that prenatal interaction with certain phthalates, such as DEHP, can alter mitochondrial function and increase the prenatal maternal non-oxidative metabolism pathways (Thomson et al., 2023), increasing the risk of oxidative stress and thus ASD traits in offspring (Usui et al., 2023). In fact, it has been shown that high prenatal phthalates levels and certain oxidative stress-related SNPs, are associated with more than a twofold increase in the risk of ASD (Ponsonby et al., 2020). In other words, the effect of phthalates on neurodevelopment is not only due to the presence of the compound itself, but also to the interaction of multiple environmental and genetic factors. Despite these findings, it has also been shown that folic acid supplementation (≥ 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$) and multivitamins during the first month of pregnancy can significantly attenuate the ASD traits associated with the presence of certain phthalates, such as MBP, MBzP, MiBP, MCP and MCOP (Oulhote et al., 2020; Shin et al., 2018). This reversal of effects by vitamin supplementation has already been seen for other toxicants, such as pesticides and pollutants (Goodrich et al., 2018; Schmidt et al., 2017), probably by protecting the fetus from depletion of certain micronutrients essential for neurogenesis, such as zinc (Liu et al., 2022) or from phthalate-induced DNA methylation changes in key neurodevelopmental genes (Ponsonby et al., 2020; Jedynak et al., 2022). Metabolomics has also shown how phthalates can lead to impaired placental lipid transport and a direct negative effect on placental carnitine and sialic acid, key for fetal neurodevelopment (Parenti et al., 2022). Although in this study we have focused on phthalates exposure during the prenatal period, it is important to note that exposure to MBP, MiBP, MEP and MBzP at an early age has negative effects on neurodevelopment, such as unusual visual behavior or poorer communication and social functioning (Rolland et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2021). There is also evidence that phthalates levels tend to decrease with age (Kim et al., 2021), and that their association with certain syndromes, such as ADHD, becomes weaker as children get older (Ku et al., 2020). The effects of phthalates on neurobehavioral outcomes identified in this review can be explained by their multiple mechanisms of action. Phthalates, such as DEHP, alter non-oxidative metabolism through the mitochondrial pyruvate carrier complex (MPC) and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPAR) (Chen et al., 2018; Kratochvil et al., 2019), increasing oxidative stress in the mother. Animal studies suggest that maternal oxidative stress alters offspring brain development through GSH depletion, lipid peroxidation and inflammatory responses (Akhtar et al., 2017). Phthalate-induced oxidative stress also leads to reduced hippocampal expression of BDNF, a factor involved in dendritic growth and synaptic plasticity, which is associated with cognitive and learning functions (Smith and Holahan, 2014). Locomotion activity and spatial memory may also be affected by the phthalates through the decrease of the levels of the *N*-methyl-*D*-aspartic acid (NMDA) receptor subunits NR1 and NR2B in the hippocampus (Dai et al., 2015). Phthalates also induce double-strand DNA break in human neurons and disrupt the thyroid signaling pathway, whereby their exposure during critical periods of brain development is associated with abnormal cortical morphology and abnormal corpus callosum development in offspring (Samadi et al., 2015; Lischinsky et al., 2016), brain structures associated with behavior and cognitive processes. Other potential pathways by which phthalates may affect neurodevelopment include the reduction of dopaminergic activity in the brain, leading to behavioral pathologies such as anxious behavior, impaired associative learning and

inhibition of social interaction (Huang et al., 2022; R. Wang et al., 2016). There appear to be inconsistencies as to which period of pregnancy is most critical for phthalate exposure, as not all studies collected samples from all trimesters of pregnancy. The first trimester is critical because the presence of phthalates leads to changes in placental DNA methylation and therefore to damage of placental tissue (LaRocca et al., 2014). This fact is confirmed in the study by Torres-Olascoaga, where they show that the first trimester is the period of greatest effect of high-molecular-weight phthalates on the cognitive abilities of four-year-old children, with motor function being the most affected ability in the MSCA test (Torres-Olascoaga et al., 2020). Although these authors did not observe an effect in the third trimester, there are studies that report that prenatal exposure to MBzP in the second and third trimesters or exposure to MnBP in the second trimester is associated with ASD features and slower processing speed (Rolland et al., 2023). Therefore, interpretation of the critical window period for the effect of phthalates on neurodevelopment is difficult due to the heterogeneity of the gestational periods and outcomes studied, as well as the metabolites analyzed and how they are measured. Neurodevelopment is likely to be influenced by multiple exposure periods because it is a dynamic process that encompasses both fetal and adulthood. For example, time windows for neurogenesis and synaptogenesis do not overlap in time, the latter developing from the second trimester to adolescence (Tau and Peterson, 2010) so it makes sense that the effect of phthalates on neurodevelopment does not have a defined critical period of exposure. These findings highlight how early life is a critical period in neurodevelopment, as previously noted (Nelson 3rd and Gabard-Durnam, 2020), and future studies using samples from children rather than just the mother are needed. It is also important to take into account certain factors that may affect neurodevelopment and that tended to be overlooked in most of the studies analyzed, such as the genetic characteristics of the population studied, exposure to other toxins and pollutants, lack of certain nutrients, the presence of chronic and severe stress during pregnancy or the existence of psychiatric disorders in the parents (Morgan et al., 2023; de Lauzon-Guillain et al., 2022; Manzari et al., 2019). Regarding the specific effects of LMWPs or HMWPs on neurodevelopment, some authors have found that mixtures of LMWPs such as DEP and DBP metabolites most significantly affect the neurobehavioral development of girls during early gestation (Day et al., 2021). Similarly, Rolland et al. found that exposure to low molecular weight phthalates such as MEP, MiBP and MnBP was associated with reduced eye tracking in girls, a characteristic feature of ASD (Rolland et al., 2023). However, it is difficult to establish specific effects as most studies do not differentiate between LMWP and HMWP in their analyses. In the present review, we found that phthalate metabolites belonging to LMWPs were associated with language delay, lower processing speed and autistic traits, while HMWPs were associated with ADHD and ASD symptoms, lower motor scores and a lower overall cognitive index. However, these conclusions are based on results from a few metabolites belonging to one group or the other. Targeted studies with a larger number of phthalates from both groups are needed to confirm these hypotheses.

We have found some limitations in conducting this review. We cannot control for publication bias, so some of the studies whose results are not as expected may not have been published. There is also a lot of variation in the timing of sample collection. Although maternal urine is the most common matrix used to quantify phthalates, very few studies follow phthalate levels throughout pregnancy, leaving aside the detection windows of susceptibility (e.g. for neurodevelopmental studies). In addition, phthalates have a short half-life and their concentration is highly variable depending on whether there are punctual exposures. Pooled within-subject measurements would be desirable to achieve lower temporal variability and higher reproducibility compared to single spot urine (Oulhote et al., 2020). It would also be interesting, in certain cases, to follow the child over a longer period of time, as was done in the study by Ku et al. (Ku et al., 2020), which followed the neurodevelopment of children between the ages of 2 and 11 years. In

this way, we could be detected a possible progression of adverse effects over time. Studying exposure to mixtures of phthalates rather than individual phthalates would also more closely reflect what we find in reality. Caution should also be exercised when using matrices other than urine to measure prenatal phthalate exposure, such as serum or maternal hair. In the former case, there may be enzymatic conversion of phthalate diesters to monoesters, so it is more advisable to measure phthalate monoesters such as MEHP rather than its parent phthalate, DEHP, to avoid underestimating the effect (Minatoya et al., 2016). In the case of hair collection, although it is a non-invasive method, it is important to know how to collect the sample correctly, as a mistake in hair length can lead to deviations in the measurement of the gestation period. Another recommendation would be to standardize the criteria used to measure the outcomes. In this review we have seen the use of several questionnaires to measure the neurodevelopment, such as the SRS to assess the severity of ASD symptoms (Alampi et al., 2021; Oulhote et al., 2020; Patti et al., 2021), the CBCL, a caregiver report form to identify problem behaviors in children (Thomson et al., 2023; Haggerty et al., 2021), the SRS-2 (Alampi et al., 2021; Oulhote et al., 2020; Day et al., 2021; Patti et al., 2021; Haggerty et al., 2021), which identifies social impairments associated with ASD, questionnaires to evaluate executive function (Choi et al., 2021) or social-emotional and adaptive behavior questionnaires such as BAYLEY-III (Ponsonby et al., 2020; Jones et al., 2018). Unifying the criteria for which questionnaires to use would facilitate comparisons between studies and therefore more robust conclusions about the effect of phthalates on infant neurodevelopment. We would also like to point out that all the studies analyzed found phthalates in the samples collected. A higher or lower presence of phthalates in the samples strongly depends on the country where the sample was collected, as it is related to the lifestyle, diet and the most commonly used phthalates in industry. For example, high levels of DEHP have been found in rivers in Taiwan (Yuan et al., 2002) or in household dust in Japan, where DEHP was the most commonly used phthalate for many years, mainly as a PVC plasticizer (Lyu et al., 2022). This highlights our daily interaction with these compounds, which are found in products as diverse as cosmetics and cleaning products. Although legislative changes have reduced exposure to these compounds, such as DEHP, DBP, DIBP and BBP (The European Commission, 2018), there is still evidence of their presence in critical areas such as the food supply chain (Edwards et al., 2022) or cosmetics (Aldegunde-Louzao et al., 2023).

Based on the results presented in this review, it is reasonable to develop comprehensive strategies aimed at reducing maternal exposure to phthalates in order to prevent all these undesirable effects on maternal and infant health, with special emphasis on populations with a lower educational and socioeconomic status (Bloom et al., 2019; Casas et al., 2016). It is also necessary to promote research on the health effects of alternative plasticizers, compounds that are replace phthalates and whose contamination in the domestic environment is already evident (Christia et al., 2019), including in pregnant women (Wenzel et al., 2021).

Abbreviations

ADHD	Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder
ASD	Autism spectrum disorder
BBzP	Butyl-benzyl phthalate
BP	Blood pressure
COX-2	Cyclooxygenase-2
DBP	Dibutyl phthalate
DBP	Diastolic blood pressure
DEEP	Bis (2-ethoxyethyl) phthalate
DEHP	Bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate;
DEP	Diethyl phthalate
DiBP	Diisobutyl phthalate
DMP	Dimethyl phthalate
DNOP	Di-n-octylphthalate
EDCs	Endocrine-disrupting compounds
EFW	Estimated fetal weight
FGR	Fetal growth restriction
GDM	Gestational diabetes mellitus
GRADE	Grades of Recommendation, Assessment, Development and Evaluation
GWG	Gestational weight gain
HMWP	High molecular weight phthalates
IGT	Impaired glucose tolerance
LMWP	Low molecular weight phthalates
LOAEL	Low observed adverse effect level
MBP	Monobutyl phthalate
MBzP	Mono-benzyl phthalate
MCOP	Mono-carboxy-isooctyl phthalate
MCPP	Mono-(3-carboxypropyl) phthalate
MECCP	Mono-2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl phthalate
MEHHP	Mono (2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate
MEHP	Mono-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate
MEOHP	Mono (2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate
MEP	Mono-ethyl phthalate
MHBP	Mono-3-hydroxybutyl phthalate
MHiBP	Mono-2-methyl-2-hydroxypropyl phthalate
MiBP	Mono-isobutyl phthalate
MMP	Monomethyl phthalate
OR	Odds ratio
PIH	Pregnancy-induced hypertension
PPARs	Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors
PTB	Preterm birth
sBP	Systolic blood pressure
SCQ	Social communication questionnaire
SGA	Small for gestational age
Sptb	Spontaneous preterm birth
SRS-2	Social responsiveness scale
T1	First trimester
T2	Second trimester
T3	Third trimester
ΣDEHP	Sum of di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.175080>.

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